

Further findings on the intergenerational transmission of alcohol consumption

Keywords: Health Behaviour | Public Health | Intergenerational transmission | Alcohol consumption | HILDA | Genetic Influences | Gender Norms | Socialisation
JEL: I12 | I18 | J13 | J16 | D10 | C21 | C23

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[Published in Health Economics](#)

First draft: February 2, 2023 | Current version: March 27, 2026

Using 43,817 parent–child pairs from 23 waves of the HILDA Survey, I study the intergenerational transmission of alcohol use within a rational model of trait transmission. Transmission is predominantly same-sex: the mother–daughter elasticity is 0.10 and the father–son elasticity is 0.09; there is no father–daughter effect. Influence peaks at ages 15–17 and re-emerges at 28–37 when offspring become parents; mothers also affect sons at both junctures. Comparisons with non-birth (adoptee-style) dyads show similar mother–daughter transmission, indicating norm-based rather than biological channels. Identification concerns are addressed with placebo reshuffling and copula-based corrections; estimates are robust across specifications. Men who remain childless are more likely to mirror maternal drinking, which—together with declining fertility and earlier alcohol-control policies—helps explain cohort declines in male drinking. The interpretation is that parental norms anchor behaviour at identity-forming and role-transition ages, with strong persistence thereafter. Policy should target these windows with gender-specific, couple-level interventions alongside population levers on price, availability and marketing.

1. Introduction

Harmful alcohol consumption remains a leading cause of health problems and hospital admissions associated with substance abuse (Sassi 2015). The societal and individual costs of alcohol misuse are substantial, with alcohol-related deaths often exceeding those caused by all other drugs combined (Rehm et al. 2009). In Australia alone—despite alcohol harm control being a longstanding public-policy priority—around 16 people die and 359 are hospitalised every day for alcohol-related reasons (AIHW 2018).

Yet the relationship between alcohol and socioeconomic outcomes is not uniformly negative: moderate drinking is associated with higher earnings and social integration, likely through networking and signalling mechanisms (Bray et al. 2018; Caliendo and Hennecke 2022; Walker and Munford 2023). This duality—where nonproblematic consumption can be socially functional while excess is harmful—means that drinking habits transmit not simply as maladaptive behaviours but as norm-mediated strategies embedded in gendered social contexts. Understanding this transmission is essential for designing policies that attenuate harmful patterns without ignoring the social incentives that sustain moderate use.

Parental influence on children’s drinking behaviour has been extensively examined, yet the resulting evidence is anything but coherent. Some studies report clear intergenerational resemblance in drinking (e.g., Kaynak et al. 2014), whereas others find no resemblance at all (e.g., Yu 2003; Sharmin et al. 2017). Even when resemblance is detected, its pattern varies sharply: in some cases daughters appear more responsive to paternal drinking (e.g.,

Significance Statement

Parental norms anchor offspring drinking at two pivotal life stages. Using 43,817 parent–child pairs from the HILDA Survey (2001–2023), I find a predominantly same-sex parental channel (mother–daughter 0.10; father–son 0.09) with no father–daughter effect, plus mother–son spillovers at ages 15–17 and again at 28–37 when sons become fathers. Comparable elasticities in non-birth dyads indicate norm-mediated rather than biological transmission, and adolescent peer contexts amplify—rather than substitute—the parental template. Policy follows directly: target adolescence and early parenthood with gender-specific, couple-level programmes, complemented by population levers on price, availability and marketing.

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Homel and Warren 2019; Windle and Windle 2012), while in others sons exhibit greater responsiveness to maternal drinking (e.g., Macleod et al. 2008). Rather than converging on a stable account of how drinking habits are transmitted, this sprawling literature has produced a set of fragmented and often contradictory findings.

Part of this fragmentation is conceptual. Explanations are frequently developed a posteriori, with theory adjusted to fit particular patterns (e.g., Campbell and Oei 2010; Skeer et al. 2011; Denton and Walters 1999; Yu and Perrine 1997). Findings of stronger daughter sensitivity are read as evidence that adolescent girls remain more other-regarding, while stronger son effects motivate a ‘male vulnerability’ hypothesis; same-sex patterns are attributed to social learning theory (e.g., Wickrama et al. 1999; Yu and Perrine 1997). These accounts are intuitively plausible but often case-specific, offering limited structure for understanding when different patterns should arise. Methodologically, the evidence base is equally diverse, spanning epidemiological designs (Aiken et al. 2015), psychological studies (Poelen et al. 2009), and a mixture of estimands, empirical strategies, and non-representative samples. This heterogeneity makes it difficult to compare results across studies and to extract general lessons about intergenerational transmission.

The current study builds upon that literature, employing econometric tools proven successful in health mobility research (e.g., Halliday 2020), which themselves build on income-mobility methods (Davis et al. 2025). I use the Household, Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia (HILDA) Survey—a nationally representative longitudinal panel with repeated, confidential self-reports of alcohol consumption collected annually via the self-completion questionnaire—providing rich, long-run measures of drinking behaviour.

To interpret the patterns that emerge, I draw on the rational model of trait transmission (Bisin and Verdier 2011, 2001), which treats transmission as strategic interaction between forward-looking parents and environment-responsive children. Building on evolutionary biology models that distinguished direct (vertical, parental) and oblique (horizontal, broader milieu) transmission (Cavalli-Sforza and Feldman 1981; Boyd and Richerson 1988), Bisin and Verdier (2000) endogenised parental decisions within an environment where parents are altruistic—as in Becker (1981)—toward offspring but experience a higher payoff when the child shares their trait. This preference asymmetry—termed cultural intolerance—motivates costly parental investment in socialisation. Children, meanwhile, adopt traits stochastically based on their exposure to vertical and oblique influences.

The oblique channel incorporates what network and conformity models emphasise: local complementarities and identity payoffs in the reference group make it individually optimal to align with salient norms (Blume et al. 2011; Akerlof and Kranton 2000). In this framework, peer forces are part of the environment that shapes parental socialisation effort, while the empirical analysis focuses on the vertical channel.

This two-channel transmission process—costly parental socialisation effort and child trait adoption shaped by both parental and broader social influences—yields rich predictions. Transmission strengthens when both parents share the same trait, as this aligns socialisation efforts—predicting positive assortative mating, whereby parents actively seek partners with similar attitudes to enhance joint transmission capacity. Empirical support is robust: assortative mating has been documented for trust and risk preference (Dohmen, Falk, Huffman, and Sunde 2011), religion (Luria and Katz 2019), and alcohol consumption itself (Verweij and Abdellaoui 2022; Howe et al. 2019; Agrawal et al. 2006). This implies that both maternal and paternal traits should be modelled jointly—a feature central to the empirical specification here.

The framework also accommodates the broader social environment by allowing the strength of cultural intolerance to vary with trait prevalence (e.g., Hauk and Saez-Marti 2002). When moderate drinking is widely accepted—even rewarded, as shown by wage premia (Auld 2005; Peters and Stringham 2006)—oblique transmission complements rather than dilutes direct transmission. This mechanism is especially relevant for drinking, which is embedded in gendered social rituals. Strong gender-specific norms—where moderate drinking signals sociability for men but risks impropriety for women—sharpen predictions: transmission should be strongest along same-sex lines, as children emulate the parent whose life trajectory most closely mirrors their own.

Applied heuristically over the life cycle, the rational model treats trait selection as a sequence of re-optimisations. As social roles and payoffs change, the salience of vertical vs. oblique sources shifts, and the effective cultural-

intolerance term varies with trait prevalence. Without committing to a fully dynamic microfoundation, this logic yields clear implications: transmission should be strongest during periods of identity formation and may re-emerge at major role transitions when individuals recalibrate behavioural norms. When norms are gendered, same-sex parental models carry higher informational value, generating asymmetric patterns even in the absence of biological channels.

Because the rational-transmission model generates intergenerational spillovers through costly socialisation and environmental learning—without invoking biology—it implies that transmission should persist when genetic ties are attenuated. This yields a sharp test: if drinking patterns continue to transmit in non-birth parent-child dyads, the evidence points to norm-mediated learning as the dominant channel. Non-birth dyads provide a design-based contrast that sharpens inference on norm-mediated transmission. The persistence of these patterns aligns with the gender-norm mechanism outlined above and supports the rational-transmission model as the most coherent explanation.

With this conceptual frame in place, the empirical analysis proceeds as follows. Section 2 describes the parent-child sample from the HILDA Survey, constructed using a data-efficient cohort-layering method (Lee and Solon 2009)—applied to this panel for the first time—which yields a sample of 43,817 offspring with both identified parents. Section 3 develops the econometric approach, jointly modelling maternal and paternal drinking and allowing flexible gender-age interactions. Section 4 reports the main estimates—no father-daughter transmission, some mother-son effects, and clear same-sex elasticities (slightly larger for females, 0.10, than males, 0.09)—and shows that drinking transmission is lower than for traits with strong parental control (e.g., religiosity) but higher than for traits more exposed to external factors (e.g., earnings, mental health, extroversion). These estimates are robust to extensive covariate adjustments, placebo tests using parent reshuffling within areas (Dohmen, Falk, Huffman, and Sunde 2011), and copula-based corrections for endogeneity (Park and Gupta 2012)—addressing causal identification concerns central to addiction research—while remaining interpretable as intergenerational elasticities, the standard metric in health mobility studies.

Next, I examine life-cycle profiles and adoptee comparisons to examine age-driven dynamics and norm-mediated transmission. The transmission at ages 15–17 contributes the most to overall transmission for both genders. Same-sex transmission evolves similarly for both genders until age 28, after which daughters experience an additional effect, particularly among childless daughters. This pattern is consistent with gender-norm channels and is further confirmed in females—but not males—using a subsample of non-birth parents. Additionally, mother-to-son transmission appears only at ages 15–17 and again at 28–37, with an additional effect among childless sons.

These results align closely with the rational-transmission logic: adolescents and young adults actively assess which parental behaviours remain adaptive within changing social roles. Consistent with this interpretation, shifting the exposure window to before age 14—a falsification exercise—yields no detectable transmission or gender-specific patterns, as drinking is integral to social engagements that younger children do not yet find relevant. Further, drinking habits—once shaped by parental influence in adolescence—prove remarkably persistent throughout adulthood. Using the full HILDA panel, intragenerational transition matrices show that individuals are roughly twice as likely to change their social status as their drinking behaviour, suggesting that the intergenerational effects estimated up to age 37 continue to structure drinking well into later life.

Taken together, the study brings mobility-style intergenerational elasticities to a setting central to addiction research, pairs them with identification checks that address endogeneity concerns, and embeds the patterns in a rational transmission framework. The contributions are threefold: a large, data-efficient parent-child panel and joint modelling of maternal and paternal drinking; mechanism evidence that locates transmission at identity-forming and role-transition ages and links asymmetries to gendered norms; and adoptee comparisons that sharpen inference on norm-mediated (non-genetic) channels. Policy relevance—discussed in Section 5 along broader implications—follows directly: interventions that are timed (adolescence and early parenthood), targeted (same-sex mentoring and couple-level programming), and context-aware (responsive to local norms) are more likely to attenuate harmful transmission than undifferentiated messages.

Table 1. Recoding for measured drinking

Reported	Recoded
How many standard drinks do you usually have?	
13 or more standard drinks	13
11-12 standard drinks	11.5
9-10 standard drinks	9.5
7-8 standard drinks	7.5
5-6 standard drinks	5.5
3-4 standard drinks	3.5
1-2 standard drinks	1.5
Do you drink alcohol?	
I have never drunk alcohol	0
I no longer drink	0
Yes, I drink alcohol every day	365
Yes, I drink alcohol 5 or 6 days per week	286
Yes, I drink alcohol 3 or 4 days per week	182
Yes, I drink alcohol 1 or 2 days per week	78
Yes, I drink alcohol 2 or 3 days per month	30
Yes, but only rarely	10

Note: Values assigned to survey answers.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023; pooled waves.

Figure 1. Drinking right skew and censoring

Notes: Drinking quantiles (blue dots) against the theoretical normal quantiles (straight grey line). Red dashed line is 72nd percentile separating hazardous and safe drinking.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023; pooled waves.

Figure 2. Validating drinking with risk preference

Notes: Binned scatterplot of drinking on risk with respondent clustered errors; figure also shows a marginal histogram of risk preference (Cattaneo et al. 2024).

Source: HILDA Survey 2014, 2018, 2022; pooled waves.

2. Data

A. Drinking data. The HILDA Survey reports drinking intensity and frequency for all waves from 2001 to 2023. In 2001, drinking is coded slightly differently, but harmonising responses across waves is straightforward. Table 1 shows the survey question and the value I assign to each answer. The final variable represents the total annual alcohol consumption for each respondent, calculated by multiplying the reported drinking frequency by drinking intensity. This measure reflects the number of standard drinks (approximately 10 grams of alcohol) consumed annually, with non-drinkers assigned a value of zero. For better clinical context, guidelines suggest up to six standard drinks weekly (313 annually) have health impacts akin to abstinence. This corresponds to the 72nd percentile of the constructed drinking measure.

The drinking measure is right-censored, as reported drinking intensity does not differentiate the number of drinks above 13. Figure 1 simultaneously illustrates censoring and skewness of the drinking measure by plotting the quantiles of drinking against the quantiles if drinking followed a normal distribution (Conroy 2005). The points clustered at the maximum confirm the presence of censoring. The cluster of values at the minimum on the left indicates a right skew. For a better perspective on the skew, the median consumption is 105, while the 89th percentile already consumes 1,000—equivalent to filling an average bathtub with beer—with a maximum value almost five times that. The right-skew complicates linear modelling, but enables endogeneity diagnostics via copula-based methods (Park and Gupta 2012), which gain better power with skewed regressors (Supplementary Section A).

B. Validating data. Self-reported drinking is generally reliable around the mean, with most concerns concentrated at distributional extremes (Northcote and Livingston 2011; Livingston and Callinan 2015). To provide a focused construct-validity check for the estimand I use (the conditional mean), Figure 2 shows that self-reported drinking covaries strongly with self-reported risk attitudes whose survey measures have been extensively externally validated (Baillon et al. 2022; Falk et al. 2018; Schildberg-Hörisch 2018; Dohmen, Falk, Huffman, Sunde, et al. 2011). I therefore read this covariance as evidence that my drinking construct aligns with a validated behavioural domain at the mean. Further, the alcohol items are collected in a self-completion questionnaire with standard-drink definitions (minimising social-desirability issues), and Australian labelling law requires the number of standard drinks on containers (aiding self-assessment). As an external check on real-world responsiveness, HILDA-based analyses reliably detects policy-driven shifts in alcohol consumption (Alexeev and Weatherburn 2021)—evidence that the measure moves with plausibly exogenous shocks.

C. Life cycle drinking. Using the full 23-wave HILDA Survey panel, I now outline basic drinking habits by life stage, gender, and generation to inform the modelling choices in Section 3.

Figure 3 shows average drinking by age. Males follow an inverted U-shape, peaking in early 50s, with discontinuities at 40 and 80. Females show two connected inverted Us, peaking in early 20s and 40s, with a dip in late 20s coinciding with average first-time motherhood (AIHW 2022). Males generally drink more, except as teenagers. This shows that modelling age as a continuous variable distorts life-cycle patterns, requiring age fixed effects interacted by gender to accurately capture trends, particularly the rise from 14 to 20 and subsequent decline in females.

Figure 4 shows average drinking across birth cohorts. The decline in drinking among those born in the 1980s and beyond is seen and is well-documented in addiction literature (e.g., Livingston et al. 2016; Pape et al. 2018; Törrönen et al. 2019). The figure clarifies that the decline is primarily male-driven, while for females born after 1995, lifelong drinking is increasing—a trend likely linked to evolving gender norms (Keyes et al. 2008). To foreshadow my results, these norms also influence intergenerational transmission. To address these trends, the model incorporates birth cohort effects interacted with gender.

D. Intergenerational sample. I employ a data-efficient approach for constructing the intergenerational sample, as proposed by Lee and Solon (2009). Table 4 illustrates how successive cohorts contribute observations across the HILDA Survey waves. The sample begins with the 1986 cohort, aged 15 in 2001, with 94 individuals observed across all 23 waves. Each subsequent wave adds data from both the same cohort as it ages and newly eligible cohorts entering the survey. For example, in the second wave, the 1986 cohort is observed again at age 16, and the 1987 cohort enters for the first time at age 15, bringing the total to 277 offspring—an increase of 183 from the first wave. This cohort-layering approach maximises data utilisation, with later cohorts contributing more observations as they experience less attrition.

Notes: The top figure shows drinking regressed on gender-interacted age and year fixed effects, excluding the constant and clustering errors at the individual level, isolating life cycle effects from secular drinking changes and accounting for repeated individual observations. Age coefficients and 95% CI are shown. The bottom figure shows drinking regressed on gender-interacted birth year and age fixed effects, without constant and using clustered errors. Birth year coefficients and 95% CI are displayed, showing cohort average, while age effects isolate life cycle differences.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023; pooled waves.

Table 2. Share of offspring observed by number of waves

	Number of waves observed							
	1	2	3–4	5–6	7–10	11–14	15–19	20–23
Sons	22%	11.4%	14.3%	10.9%	17.3%	13.3%	6.3%	2.3%
Daughters	23.6%	11.3%	14.2%	10.2%	15.9%	12.5%	7.2%	3%

Note: Percent of offspring observed by number of waves.
Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023; intergenerational sample.

offspring is observed varies widely: 22% of sons and 23.6% of daughters appear in only one wave, while just 2.3% of sons and 3% of daughters are observed in 20 or more waves. The bulk of the sample is concentrated in the lower end of the distribution—over one-third of offspring are seen in two or fewer waves—reflecting the trade-off between longitudinal depth and sample breadth inherent in the cohort-layering design. The full intergenerational sample includes 6,650 unique offspring with complete maternal and paternal drinking data, contributing 43,817 person-wave observations.

For observations with parental data, parental drinking is defined as the average consumption (separately for mother and father) when offspring are aged 12–18. This multiyear measure better captures the parental environment by reducing bias from short-term abstinence or reporting errors (Mazumder 2005). The average parental ages—52 for

The intergenerational sample layers birth-year cohorts to expand coverage, but data on older offspring (aged 37 in 2023) come solely from the 1986 cohort, limiting observations for the oldest individuals. As shown in Table 2, the number of waves in which each

Table 3. Descriptive statistics

Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	Min	0.25	Med	0.75	Max	N	Mean	S.D.	Min	0.25	Med	0.75	Max
	Sons								Daughters							
Offspring drinking	21318	270.63	497.7	0	0	75	285	4745	22499	141.12	283.9	0	0	35	165	4745
Paternal drinking	21318	253.02	393.8	0	9	101	329	4235	22499	253.21	399.7	0	10	99	327	4745
Maternal drinking	21318	113.97	210.1	0	6	30	132	2717	22499	108.72	192.4	0	6	28	124	2373
Postcode drinking	21310	309.77	123.6	0	235	301	373	1625	22483	307.71	124.4	0	236	296	370	1596
Schooling	19832	11.85	1.8	0	11	12	12	19	20915	12.27	2.0	0	11	12	12	19
Equivalent HH income	21318	60.92	38.1	-203	37	54	77	828	22499	61.04	43.1	-1211	37	54	76	872
BMI	19227	24.89	5.3	11	21	24	27	67	20130	24.89	6.0	9	21	23	27	89
General health	21236	73.78	18.2	0	62	77	87	100	22434	70.05	19.4	0	57	72	82	100
Single	21318	0.80	0.4	0	1	1	1	1	22499	0.73	0.4	0	0	1	1	1
Number of minors	21318	0.99	1.2	0	0	1	2	10	22499	1.02	1.2	0	0	1	2	10
Club member	21318	0.42	0.5	0	0	0	1	1	22499	0.36	0.5	0	0	0	1	1
Not smoking	21318	0.82	0.4	0	1	1	1	1	22499	0.86	0.3	0	1	1	1	1
Openness to experience	20260	4.28	1.1	1	4	4	5	7	21639	4.24	1.0	1	4	4	5	7
Extraversion	20260	4.47	1.0	1	4	5	5	7	21644	4.58	1.1	1	4	5	5	7
Religion is not important	21318	0.49	0.5	0	0	0	1	1	22499	0.43	0.5	0	0	0	1	1
Never go to church	21318	0.61	0.5	0	0	1	1	1	22499	0.56	0.5	0	0	1	1	1
Non-birth father	21318	0.08	0.3	0	0	0	0	1	22499	0.08	0.3	0	0	0	0	1
Non-birth mother	21318	0.03	0.2	0	0	0	0	1	22499	0.03	0.2	0	0	0	0	1

Notes: Descriptive statistics for the variables used for the transmission analysis. Income is in thousands. HH stands for household.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023; intergenerational sample.

fathers and 49 for mothers—align with peak consumption, minimising bias shown in Grawe (2006). Observations missing drinking information for either parent are excluded, restricting the intergenerational sample to offspring with both parents identified.

Table 3 presents descriptive statistics by offspring gender (sons: left; daughters: right), beginning with offspring and parental drinking, followed by covariates. Some control variables are unavailable in all waves. Religion, whether offspring were raised by birth or non-birth parents, and personality type are taken from the waves closest to the wave with missing information. Postcode drinking is calculated as a leave-out mean on a pooled 23-year sample, mitigating small-sample correlations in postcodes with few respondents. Equivalent household income, derived from the Cross-National Equivalent File, accounts for taxes, transfers, and household size, calculated as the combined post-tax and transfer income of all family members divided by the square root of household size.

E. Coding parent type. The HILDA Survey records relationship-to-parent via self-reports with several non-birth labels (adoptive, step, foster, grandparent, other). While cross-sectional HILDA data show only about 1% of respondents with non-birth fathers (and half that for adoptive mothers), the cohort-layering approach yields a larger sample of non-birth parents. This occurs because offspring with non-birth parents are favourably distributed across birth cohorts, a feature that becomes fully apparent only when multiple cohorts are pooled together.

Because these labels are unguided and often conflated in practice (e.g., adoptive or foster can in fact capture kinship care by grandparents or other relatives), fine categories are both sparse and noisy; note, for example, non-trivial shares recorded as ‘no parent’ (fathers 0.11%, mothers 0.64%). The reliably observed, behaviorally meaningful contrast in these data is birth vs. non-birth. I therefore code a single non-birth indicator for each parent and report raw category shares in Table 5 for transparency.

This coding aligns with administrative studies (Björklund et al. 2006), where sources typically observe only whether

Table 4. Age and birth year by wave

Wave	N	Age		Year of birth	
		Min	Max	Min	Max
2001	94	15	15	1986	1986
2002	277	15	16	1986	1987
2003	435	15	17	1986	1988
2004	588	15	18	1986	1989
2005	776	15	19	1986	1990
2006	968	15	20	1986	1991
2007	1073	15	21	1986	1992
2008	1185	15	22	1986	1993
2009	1378	15	23	1986	1994
2010	1585	15	24	1986	1995
2011	1913	15	25	1986	1996
2012	2052	15	26	1986	1997
2013	2232	15	27	1986	1998
2014	2411	15	28	1986	1999
2015	2515	15	29	1986	2000
2016	2790	15	30	1986	2001
2017	2835	15	31	1986	2002
2018	2900	15	32	1986	2003
2019	3073	15	33	1986	2004
2020	3134	15	34	1986	2005
2021	3176	15	35	1986	2006
2022	3126	15	36	1986	2007
2023	3275	15	37	1986	2008
Total	43817	15	37	1986	2008

Note: Minimum and maximum ages and birth years by HILDA Survey wave in the intergenerational sample.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023; intergenerational sample.

a parent is birth or not, and identification rests on that same split. In Table 3, the final two rows use this aggregated indicator, keeping the descriptive analysis focused on the clearest, high-power contrast supported by both the survey design and common administrative practice.

3. Methodology

A. Econometric problem. Estimating substantively meaningful and econometrically credible drinking transmission poses several challenges. Drinking is highly right-skewed with mass points, making ordinary least squares (OLS) estimator fragile (Chen and Roth 2023). Quantile regression estimator accommodates skewness (Schmidt and Tauchmann 2011; Karlsson et al. 2016) but is ill-suited for intergenerational elasticity, which is a mean-based parameter (Jäntti and Jenkins 2015, p. 839).

Rank-rank regression (RRR), as in Andersen (2021), is also problematic. The conditioning undermines RRR’s interpretive benefits, notably by not constraining its parameter to the unit interval (Chernozhukov et al. 2024). Point masses in the drinking distributions—the horizontal lines in Figure 1—complicate inference, requiring additional complexities in handling ties (Chetverikov and Wilhelm 2023). The interpretation is also unclear. Unlike income, where RRR points to how a child’s income position is affected by their parents’, the clinical relevance of a child’s position in a drinking distribution is far less clear. RRR’s key advantage lies in its invariance to relative dispersion between generations, which is crucial in income mobility studies due to generational differences in inequality. Presently, the relative standard deviations of drinking across generations for a given gender are similar, rendering RRR less useful.

For identification (Lundberg et al. 2021), the rational model of trait transmission (Bisin and Verdier 2011) treats vertical influence as originating directly from parents, uniquely identifiable and conceptually distinct from age, cohort, peers, siblings, partners, or extended kin. The model implies a joint-exposure estimand: maternal and paternal drinking must enter together to avoid omitted-variable bias from parental sorting and environment selection (including assortative mating). Accordingly, the analysis is restricted to offspring for whom both parents’ drinking can be observed, yielding a coherent estimate of the causal parental transmission parameter. One-parent cases—included for transparency in Supplementary Table C.3—mix the estimand with heterogeneous family structures and non-vertical channels.

B. Baseline specification. To address these challenges, I use an exponential regression model estimated via Poisson pseudo-maximum likelihood (PPML, Silva and Tenreiro 2022), recommended for transmission analysis (Mitnik and Grusky 2020). The model specification is:

$$\ln(E(Y_{iagy}^o|\cdot)) = \delta_{ag} + \sigma_{yg} + \beta_g^p Y_i^p + \beta_g^m Y_i^m \quad [1]$$

Here, i stands for an offspring-parent dyad, Y_{iagy}^o , Y_i^p , and Y_i^m are drinking, respectively, of offspring, father, and mother. Parental drinking only varies by i , reflecting the averaging of these variables over the offspring’s age 12–18. The offspring drinking varies by the offspring age a , gender g , and the offspring year of birth y . Thus, the equation includes age and year of birth fixed effects δ_{ag} and σ_{yg} , which are interacted by gender as shown by the subscript g . The β coefficients, which are of primary interest, are also interacted by gender. This exhaustive array of fixed effects controls nonparametrically for life-cycle and birth year drinking disparities.

No additional controls are included to avoid collider bias, aligning with intergenerational income persistence literature. This approach is particularly relevant for drinking, given the lack of consensus on risky health behaviour

Table 5. Types of parents

	Father		Mother	
	N	%	N	%
	Birth			
Birth	42459	96.9	40178	91.7
	Non-birth			
Adoptive	150	0.34	207	0.47
Step	197	0.45	2165	4.94
Other	36	0.08	52	0.12
Grandparent	27	0.06	39	0.09
Uncle/aunt	6	0.01	5	0.01
Foster	40	0.09	36	0.08
No parent	49	0.11	282	0.64
Missing	853	1.95	853	1.95
Total	43817	100	43817	100

Note: All parent types except birth are coded as non-birth in Table 3.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023; intergenerational sample.

conceptualisation (Cawley and Ruhm 2011). Health capital and peer effects models suggest conflicting controls. Schmidt and Tauchmann’s (2011) influential drinking study also omits other control variables.

To align with existing literature (Jäntti and Jenkins 2015), the estimates are reported as elasticities, computed as numerical derivatives (Baum 2010; Boggess and MacDonald 2013). This method uses the estimated conditional mean function to calculate proportional changes in the dependent variable for proportional changes in independent variables, correctly handling zeros and aligning with Wooldridge’s (1992) recommendation. Focusing on elasticities makes the exact definition of drinking irrelevant as long as it’s consistent across generations. Following Lee and Solon (2009), I cluster standard errors by offspring using the CV1 estimator.

Evidence consistent with the correct specification of [1] and with the exogeneity of the parental drinking regressors is presented in the Results section. Supplementary Section A provides additional supporting check on these points, while Supplementary Section B reports robustness to alternative inference procedures and offers a design-based justification for the clustering approach.

4. Results

A. Baseline results. Table 6 presents two sets of estimates using offspring-clustered standard errors with gender-specific age and birth-year fixed effects, excluding additional controls. The top panel reports average marginal effects from the PPML estimator, directly comparable to the OLS results in Supplementary Table A.1. That table also shows that copula-based endogeneity corrections produce elasticities statistically indistinguishable from the baseline. PPML estimates are more efficient and slightly smaller in magnitude than OLS, reflecting the variance of the error term being proportional to the conditional mean, a condition met by the data.

The findings indicate that a 10% increase in maternal drinking corresponds to a 1.0% increase in daughters’ drinking, with suggestive evidence of a 0.2% increase for sons. The same change in paternal drinking corresponds to a 0.9% increase for sons, with no detectable effect for daughters. I then test three theory-guided contrasts and report each null with its p-value (two-sided Wald tests, cluster-robust variance): (i) equality across the four parent-child dyads ($p = 0.0033$); (ii) equality of same-sex elasticities (father-son vs. mother-daughter; $p = 0.71$); (iii) equality of same-sex average marginal effects ($p = 0.004$). Supplementary Table B.1 shows alternative inference methods. All subsequent tables and figures report PPML estimates as elasticities.

To contextualise these findings amidst inconsistent methodologies across studies, I leverage the HILDA Survey’s data richness, applying the same method used for drinking to other right-skewed traits. Parental variables are averaged for offspring aged 12–18, with data points restricted to those used for drinking estimates, and age-gender and cohort-gender fixed effects included. Table 7 show the resulting elasticities comparable to baseline drinking estimates.

Drinking transmission lies between traits that are more malleable to parental influence (e.g., religiosity) and those shaped mainly by external forces (e.g., earnings, mental health). This intermediate position accords with the logic of cultural intolerance in the rational-transmission model: given a level of parental investment, transmission is strongest where parents can exert direct control and weakest where institutional constraints dominate.

Table 6. Baseline estimates

	Dependent variable: Offspring drinking				N
	Paternal drinking		Maternal drinking		
PPML—average marginal effects					
Son	0.098***	(0.019)	0.059+	(0.033)	43,817
Daughter	0.014	(0.013)	0.125***	(0.024)	
PPML—elasticities at means (baseline)					
Son	0.092***	(0.017)	0.024+	(0.014)	43,817
Daughter	0.024	(0.023)	0.099***	(0.018)	

Table 7. Contrasting drinking with other traits

	Paternal trait		Maternal trait		N
Mental health					
Son	-0.001	(0.009)	0.041***	(0.010)	43,737
Daughter	-0.004	(0.011)	0.047***	(0.013)	
Openness to experience					
Son	0.039**	(0.013)	0.007	(0.012)	39,476
Daughter	0.036**	(0.014)	0.007	(0.012)	
Individual labour earnings					
Son	0.045***	(0.014)	0.062***	(0.015)	43,817
Daughter	0.037***	(0.011)	0.079***	(0.011)	
Time spent playing with your kid					
Son	0.157**	(0.054)	0.046	(0.064)	39,305
Daughter	0.038	(0.049)	0.164**	(0.052)	
Importance of religion					
Son	0.313***	(0.035)	0.139***	(0.027)	40,210
Daughter	0.338***	(0.029)	0.124***	(0.020)	

+ $p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Note: Table 6 reports Model [1] with two types of marginal effects; Table 7 applies the same model to alternative traits.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023; intergenerational sample.

Interpretation: Transmission is predominantly same-sex, with a smaller but suggestive mother-son spillover. Drinking transmission is clinically meaningful and exceeds that of several commonly studied traits.

B. Baseline robustness. Table 8 addresses the right-side censoring in Figure 1 using likelihood-function adjustments (Hardin and Hilbe 2018, Ch. 14). Results match the baseline, indicating that the HILDA Survey’s top-coding does not compromise internal validity. A truncated-regression check, under an alternative missing-data assumption, yields the same conclusion.

Table 9 illustrates why the baseline jointly models the two parental channels. Estimating each dyad separately distorts the underlying family structure and produces transmission coefficients that shift markedly with covariate choice. Similar instability arises when incomplete dyads are included with missing-parent indicators (Supplementary Table C.3), where movements in elasticities includes selection and composition issues. Prior studies commonly combine these two practices—separating dyads while also mixing complete and incomplete families (e.g., Windle and Windle 2012)—which helps explain the inconsistencies seen in the earlier literature.

Table 10 examines the impact of offspring controls on baseline estimates. All controls are interacted by gender and added in sets. For instance, the table’s bottom shows results when two gender-interacted indicators are added to Equation (1): one for offspring claiming religion is unimportant, and another for those never attending church (cf., Adlaf and Smart 1985). Other sets of control variables include postcode drinking (cf., McLaughlin et al. 2016), labour market outcomes (cf., Auld 2005), health status (cf., Rehm et al. 2010), marriage market outcomes (cf., Stack and Bankowski 1994), social context (cf., Johnson and Jennison 1992) and personality type (cf., Kuntsche et al. 2006).

Table 10. Intergenerational drinking elasticity—influence of controls

		Dependent variable: Offspring drinking				
		Paternal drinking		Maternal drinking		N
Postcode drinking	Son	0.077***	(0.017)	0.018	(0.014)	43,793
	Daughter	0.010	(0.022)	0.089***	(0.018)	
Earnings	Son	0.085***	(0.017)	0.028*	(0.014)	40,747
	Daughter	0.027	(0.023)	0.097***	(0.019)	
Schooling	Son	0.087***	(0.017)	0.028*	(0.014)	39,245
	Daughter	0.018	(0.023)	0.098***	(0.017)	
BMI	Son	0.094***	(0.017)	0.026+	(0.014)	43,817
	Daughter	0.027	(0.023)	0.095***	(0.018)	
General health	Son	0.066***	(0.016)	0.026*	(0.012)	43,487
	Daughter	0.024	(0.021)	0.083***	(0.017)	
Married	Son	0.089***	(0.017)	0.027*	(0.014)	41,899
	Daughter	0.023	(0.023)	0.094***	(0.020)	
Openness to experience	Son	0.081***	(0.017)	0.020	(0.014)	42,313
	Daughter	0.019	(0.023)	0.090***	(0.018)	

+ p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.

Note: Results include additional gender-specific controls.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023; intergenerational sample.

Interpretation: Stability across control sets (likely colliders) suggests that the baseline model is not driven by omitted-variable bias.

confirms that shared factors—a central concern in addiction research—do not contaminate the estimates. This aligns with the stability seen in Table 10, but, as noted earlier, the stability breaks down when dyads are modelled separately or when incomplete dyads are included.

Maternal transmission to sons consistently shows a significant coefficient, with the significance varying from a suggestion of evidence to weak evidence, suggesting essential heterogeneity in this effect. This further motivates

Table 8. Influence of right-censoring

		Dependent variable: Offspring drinking				
		Paternal drinking		Maternal drinking		N
Right-censored PPML						
Son		0.092***	(0.017)	0.024+	(0.014)	43,817
	Daughter	0.024	(0.023)	0.099***	(0.018)	
Right-truncated PPML						
Son		0.092***	(0.017)	0.024+	(0.014)	43,817
	Daughter	0.024	(0.023)	0.099***	(0.018)	

Table 9. Influence of alternative dyads modelling

		Dependent variable: Offspring drinking				
		Paternal drinking		Maternal drinking		N
Son		0.104***	(0.015)	0.060***	(0.012)	19,724
	Daughter	0.072***	(0.016)	0.106***	(0.014)	

+ p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.

Notes: Table 8 reports results after modifying the maximum likelihood function for censoring or truncation. Table 9 reports results after each parameter is estimated on four sub-samples (e.g., son-father, son-mother).

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023; intergenerational sample.

Interpretation: Results are robust to censorship, and jointly specifying parental drinking is critical.

As discussed, the model without covariates is preferred, as controls likely reflect influences from parental drinking, potentially attenuating transmission estimates. Area controls may also be biased by the self-selection of heavier drinkers into high-drinking regions. Adding control sets yields estimates similar to the baseline, indicating control-covariate inclusion stability and suggesting minimal bias from endogeneity or measurement error. However, since Oster (2019) shows that this stability argument relies on unverifiable assumptions, Supplementary Section B follows Dohmen, Falk, Huffman, and Sunde (2011, p. 664) in reshuffling parents within area cells. The disappearance of transmission after reshuffling

the exploration in the subsequent subsection, which elucidates that this heterogeneity manifests during critical life stages like middle adolescence and early parenthood.

C. The role of age. Figure 5 plots elasticities from interacting parental drinking with offspring age. Although imprecision masks an interpretable profile, there is clear heterogeneity by age and gender. To summarise this more efficiently, Table 11 parameterises age using a linear spline with three knots, creating four age groups and assuming linear transmission within each segment. For example, the coefficient of 0.0066 for sons aged 15–17 is the annual effect, implying a total two-year effect of roughly twice this magnitude.

The strongest transmission of drinking habits occurs in middle adolescence (15–17). This is when young people initiate complex social interactions, experiment with risky behaviours, and become highly sensitive to social norms (Casey et al. 2008). Almost all offspring in this age range live with their parents, so trait acquisition can occur through intensive observation of parental drinking in precisely the context where drinking becomes behaviourally salient.

Point estimates indicate that same-sex transmission declines with age but becomes slightly stronger for daughters than sons by 18–21 (0.0053 vs. 0.0050), consistent with earlier female maturation and earlier uptake of complex social behaviours (Lim et al. 2013; Reeves 2022). The sharpest differences appear at 28–37 and depend on whether the offspring have children. Fathers significantly influence adult sons who are parents (0.0049), whereas the paternal effect is indistinguishable from zero for sons without children (0.0017). Mothers influence daughters throughout, with effects for daughters without children (0.0027) and stronger effects for daughters who are parents (0.0049). This helps to account for the second peak in female transmission observed in Figure 3: early adulthood and motherhood involve complex role demands, and women appear to draw on their mothers’ behaviours to navigate these transitions (Wolfe 2009; Killingsworth 2006; Meurk et al. 2014).

Mothers also influence sons. Maternal effects for sons are sizeable in middle adolescence (15–17; 0.0029). At 28–37, these effects are clearly detectable for sons who are parents (0.0015) and suggestive for sons without children (0.0015, one-sided $p \approx 0.049$). Daughters never adopt paternal drinking habits. For sons with children, there is instead a notable shift towards paternal models alongside maternal ones (0.0049 plus 0.0015), consistent with role-congruent learning at the onset of fatherhood (Habib 2012). Future work could examine whether the gender of the offspring’s own child further moderates these patterns.

A related question is what shapes lifelong drinking patterns, particularly the peak around age 50, once direct parental influence has tapered. Applying intragenerational mobility methods (Jäntti and Jenkins 2015, Sec. 10.3.1), Table 12 shows that drinking habits formed by ages 24–34 largely capture patterns at 35–54, in line with addiction literature on early habit formation (Maggs and Schulenberg 2005; Hingson et al. 2006). The transition matrices average drinking over ages 24–34 and 35–54 for the same individuals across 23 waves of the HILDA Survey. The heavy mass on the main diagonal indicates strong persistence: for example, 75% of low-level drinkers at 24–34 remain low-level at 35–54, while transitions between low and high levels are only 2–3%.

Table 11. Estimates by offspring age trends

Dependent variable: Offspring standard drinks				
Age	Paternal drinking		Maternal drinking	
	Son	Daughter	Son	Daughter
Interaction by continuous age and age groups				
15–17	0.0066*** (0.0014)	0.0013 (0.0022)	0.0029* (0.0014)	0.0061*** (0.0012)
18–21	0.0050*** (0.0009)	0.0005 (0.0009)	0.0007 (0.0006)	0.0053*** (0.0007)
22–27	0.0037*** (0.0009)	0.0009 (0.0012)	0.0009 (0.0008)	0.0034*** (0.0008)
28–37	0.0021+ (0.0012)	0.0018 (0.0019)	0.0012 (0.0009)	0.0034* (0.0013)
Additional interaction for having children				
28–37	0.0017 (0.0013)	0.0021 (0.0017)	0.0015+ (0.0009)	0.0027* (0.0012)
No kids				
28–37	0.0049*** (0.0008)	0.0007 (0.0011)	0.0015* (0.0006)	0.0049*** (0.0008)
Yes kids				
N	43,817			

+ $p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Notes: The figure includes 95% CIs, excluding cross-gender dyads to avoid clutter. The table’s top displays interactions with continuous age for four groups. The bottom includes additional interaction for having children in the oldest age group.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023; intergenerational sample.

Interpretation: Transmission peaks during adolescence and early parenthood, with maternal-to-son spillover evident in these critical phases.

The diagonal values (75–58–77) substantially exceed corresponding Australian intragenerational (58–30–57) (Kaplan et al. 2018, Table 2) and intergenerational (44–37–46) income transitions (Alexeev 2020, Table 3). The normalised trace measure of mobility (lower values indicate more persistence) is 0.45 for drinking versus 0.87 and 0.76 for intra-

Table 12. Intragenerational persistence

		Age 35–54			
		Low	Med	High	
Age 24–34	Low	75%	22%	2%	All
		75%	23%	2%	Females
		76%	21%	3%	Males
Med	22%	58%	20%	All	
	21%	58%	21%	Females	
	21%	57%	21%	Males	
High	3%	19%	77%	All	
	3%	20%	77%	Females	
	3%	22%	76%	Males	

Notes: Cross-tabulation of the relative frequencies (drinking tertiles) of drinking when individuals are 24–34 and 35–54. The package by Savegnago (2016) is used in calculations.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023; pooled waves.

Interpretation: Drinking shows extreme persistence throughout life, ≈2 times higher than that of income.

drinking becomes behaviourally salient—middle adolescence and the transition to parenthood—and much less so in between. Drinking habits set at these phases remain highly persistent, so that a relatively short window of intergenerational influence helps structure patterns well into later life, while earlier childhood exposure plays a more limited role and shows inconsistent gender-specific effects.

D. The role of norms. Extending the rational-transmission framework, intergenerational resemblance arises from parental effort and norm-mediated learning rather than biology per se. This is plausible for drinking, which—when moderate—often functions as social capital (signalling affiliation, facilitating networking) rather than pure risk (Bray et al. 2018; Caliendo and Hennecke 2022; Walker and Munford 2023). Under this view, children may emulate parental drinking to navigate gendered social environments even without genetic ties.

This perspective yields testable implications for the birth–non-birth contrast: transmission should persist in dyads with reduced genetic link if norms and socialisation carry the trait; any attenuation should be larger where the non-birth context less closely mirrors the offspring’s gendered role; and already-weak cross-gender channels should remain small. Because gender norms tend to bind more tightly for women than for men (Holmila and Raitasalo 2005; Greaves et al. 2022; Pauley et al. 2024), we should expect pronounced mother-to-daughter persistence across birth status and a comparatively weaker father-to-son link in non-birth dyads.

I use the standard adoptee-style split as a design-based check with strong precedent (Sacerdote 2011; Plug 2004; Björklund et al. 2006; Thompson 2014), interpreting it first through the rational framework—namely, as evidence on whether norm-mediated transmission survives without a direct biological tie. Empirically, I estimate the baseline specification and interact parental drinking with indicators for birth vs. non-birth for fathers and mothers, including flexible fixed effects for non-birth parent types by offspring sex to preserve comparability with the baseline model while isolating the biological vs. non-biological contrast.

and intergenerational income (Jäntti and Jenkins 2015, p. 840), implying that individuals are roughly twice as likely to change their social status as their drinking habits. Once established in early adulthood, including under parental influence, drinking patterns are highly persistent.

To conclude the role of age, Table 13 varies the parental exposure window from adolescence (12–18) back into childhood (8–14, 4–10, 1–6). The same-gender channels attenuate steadily as exposure shifts earlier. Cross-gender patterns are weaker and non-monotonic: father-to-daughter is detectable only at 8–14, vanishing at 4–10 and 1–6, while mother-to-son is small at 12–18, rises at 8–14 and 4–10, and then falls at 1–6. Overall, exposure earlier than adolescence yields smaller elasticities than the adolescent benchmark, which is at odds with a widespread account emphasising stronger effects from very early exposure to parental drinking (e.g., Donovan and Molina 2011).

Taken together, these findings are consistent with the rational-transmission view. Parental drinking exerts its strongest causal influence at the points where

Table 13. The age of exposure

Dependent variable: Offspring drinking					
	Paternal drinking		Maternal drinking		N
Parental drinking at offspring age 8–14					
Son	0.049**	(0.016)	0.034**	(0.011)	43,817
Daughter	0.046**	(0.017)	0.058***	(0.010)	
Mean	178.27		78.30		
Parental drinking at offspring age 4–10					
Son	0.030**	(0.011)	0.038***	(0.008)	43,817
Daughter	0.012	(0.011)	0.037***	(0.007)	
Mean	92.40		37.27		
Parental drinking at offspring age 1–6					
Son	0.018**	(0.006)	0.021***	(0.005)	43,817
Daughter	0.008	(0.005)	0.018**	(0.005)	
Mean	42.81		15.74		

+ p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.

Notes: Results when parental drinking is averaged over different offspring ages. Mean values for parental drinking are also shown.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023; intergenerational sample.

Interpretation: Transmission weakens for earlier ages, challenging early exposure harm theory while supporting baseline estimates and the rational view of transmission.

Table 14 summarises the results. For men, the father-to-son association weakens and becomes imprecise in non-birth dyads (0.10 vs. 0.05). For women, the mother-to-daughter association is stable across biological status (≈ 0.10 in both). Cross-gender channels are small or absent.

The pattern is robust. As shown in Supplementary Section C, the female persistence and male attenuation remain when adding offspring-level controls, varying the fixed-effects structure, and jackknifing by excluding non-birth categories (step, foster, kin, grandparent) one at a time. In every case, daughters mirror mothers regardless of biological ties, whereas sons' responsiveness to fathers largely vanishes in non-birth dyads.

Reading the birth-non-birth contrast primarily as a behavioural test of the rational model avoids committing to a mechanical genetics-environment variance decomposition (Sacerdote 2011). To map this behavioural contrast into that classical language, I adopt one auxiliary assumption: non-birth placement is approximately random with respect to drinking-related traits. Two facts make this plausible. First, robustness to offspring controls (see Supplementary Table C.1) reduces concerns about selection on observables. Second, population-register adoption studies where birth/non-birth links and pre-placement traits are observed typically find limited bias from selective placement in comparisons of adoptees and biological children (Björklund et al. 2006). Under this reading, environmental/normative factors dominate for women, whereas male transmission may include a biological or very early-life component.

This accords with prior evidence while sharpening it by gender. Adoption-based analyses often find drinking to be largely environmentally determined (Sacerdote 2007) but commonly pool men and women, potentially masking asymmetry. By estimating sex-specific elasticities across birth status, I show that the environmental channel is especially salient for women, whereas for men the father-to-son link weakens in non-birth dyads, consistent with a residual biological or very early-life component; related work documents partial biological underpinnings of male drinking (Clites et al. 2023). Finally, Hinnoosaar and Liu (2022) estimate that roughly half of drinking variation is environmental, broadly consistent with the magnitudes implied here for males.

Taken together, the results support the gendered-norm logic of the rational model: daughters adopt maternal behaviours through social learning within more tightly regulated female normative contexts, while sons' resemblance to fathers is more contingent on biological or household factors that weaken when the paternal tie is non-birth. This pattern of more intense social pressures is also echoed in Table 7, where mother-to-daughter transmission of mental health traits highlights sensitivity to societal expectations, contrasting with the more genetically driven traits like openness to experience seen in males.

5. Conclusion

Drinking transmission is overwhelmingly same-sex: mother-to-daughter (≈ 0.10) and father-to-son (≈ 0.09), with no detectable father-to-daughter transmission. The slight female advantage likely reflects tighter normative regulation of women's drinking—echoing episodes such as the rapid shifts in Eastern European women's smoking after the Soviet collapse as gender norms changed (Lillard and Dorofeeva 2015). Mothers also influence sons during adolescence and early parenthood, when sons update behaviours in unfamiliar social terrain. This pattern accords with rational transmission models in which children adjust traits when environments demand behavioural updating (Bisin and Verdier 2011).

Transmission concentrates in two life stages. At 15–17, both same-sex channels are active, and there is a maternal spillover to sons. At 28–37, effects re-emerge selectively: fathers shape sons who are parents, while mothers influence daughters regardless of parental status. Sons without children show no paternal effect at 28–37,

Table 14. Environmental channel check

	Dependent variable: Offspring drinking				N
	Paternal drinking		Maternal drinking		
	Birth	Non-birth	Birth	Non-birth	
Son	0.100*** (0.019)	0.047 (0.029)	0.022 (0.014)	0.018 (0.033)	43,817
Daughter	0.026 (0.023)	-0.008 (0.049)	0.098*** (0.020)	0.100*** (0.024)	
Parents N	40,178	3,639	42,459	1,358	

+ p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.

Notes: Results show interactions of parental drinking with birth/non-birth status and adding gender-specific fixed effects for all parent types. The number of parents is also shown.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023, intergenerational sample.

Interpretation: Sons show weaker transmission from non-birth fathers, implying genetic influence. Daughters' consistent transmission across parent types suggests environmental (gender norms) dominance.

consistent with the continued salience of earlier maternal influence. Adoptee-style comparisons are consistent with a norm-mediated mechanism: mother-to-daughter transmission persists regardless of biological ties, whereas father-to-son links attenuate in non-birth dyads. Taken together with robustness checks (controls, fixed-effects variants, leave-one-type-out), female transmission appears more norm-mediated, while for males the pattern is consistent with a residual biological or very early-life component.

Two intervention windows are clear: middle adolescence and the transition to parenthood. Delivery should align with schools/tertiary settings and perinatal/child-health touchpoints. Content should leverage the observed channels—mother-daughter and father-son modelling—with an added mother-son component in adolescence and at the onset of parenthood. Because home environments are jointly produced, brief couple-level modules (e.g., goals for home drinking, alcohol-free routines) are likely to outperform parent-only messages. For women—where transmission appears more norm-sensitive—policy should create alcohol-light substitutes for social capital (e.g., networking formats without alcohol), while for men—where normative regulation is weaker—pair messaging with environmental nudges (availability, salience at home). Population levers (price, availability, marketing) can yield intergenerational dividends through parental modelling.

The findings reframe transmission as purposive learning, not failed prevention. Children adopt parental drinking because it appears adaptive in gendered social environments. The policy challenge is altering structural incentives that make alcohol instrumental to participation, not correcting individual failures.

The detected intergenerational patterns help account for the puzzling post-1980s decline in male drinking. First, alcohol-control policies that expanded in the 1970s (Treno et al. 2014) plausibly propagated across generations via same-sex parental modelling. Second, falling fertility (ABS 2021) increased the share of men who remain childless through the ages when paternal transmission typically re-emerges. In my data, childless men do not pick up paternal habits at 28-37 but exhibit maternal influence; because mothers drink less on average, a larger share of childless men shifts male drinking downward. Policy and demography move in the same direction and match the timing of cohort declines.

The analysis focuses on two-parent households, where both maternal and paternal drinking are observed and modelled jointly. Within the rational-transmission framework, this is the setting in which the vertical channel is most clearly defined and where assortative mating and joint socialisation align naturally with the empirical specification. It is also the configuration in which endogeneity appears empirically limited: placebo tests, copula-based corrections, and robustness checks all point to small residual bias in the complete-dyad sample, whereas including incomplete dyads introduces signs of selection and heterogeneity that no longer map cleanly onto causal parental transmission.

Single-parent families may well operate through distinct mechanisms—different role models, differences in socialisation intensity, or compensatory behaviours—that cannot be cleanly captured within the joint-parent framework used here. Because incomplete dyads pool diverse pathways (solo parenting, non-co-residence, attrition, and reporting gaps), their coefficients conflate transmission with selection into these family structures. In this sense, the focus on complete dyads is both a limitation and a deliberate design choice: it isolates the mechanism the theory speaks to, avoids conflating heterogeneous processes, and yields a conditional-mean transmission parameter aligned with the intergenerational-mobility literature.

As with any linkable-dyad design, the analytic sample—though drawn from a representative survey—is not guaranteed to be nationally representative (Fitzgerald 2011), especially once restricted to complete two-parent dyads. The HILDA Survey's child and young-adult cohorts are broadly representative, with deviations mainly from recent-immigrant undercoverage (Watson 2022), but this need not carry over mechanically to the complete-dyad subsample. In this framework, however, the complete-dyad design provides the clearest and most credible link between theory and causal interpretation.

A. Causality

Endogeneity in intergenerational drinking transmission may arise from measurement errors in self-reported drinking and unobserved factors influencing both parental and offspring drinking. The estimates in Table 10 demonstrate stability across diverse covariates, suggesting minimal bias. However, since the consistency of both point and uncertainty estimates in Generalised Linear Model estimators depends on correctly specifying the conditional mean function, I now address this issue more directly.

Consider the linear analogue of the model from Section 3, $\tilde{Y}_i^o = \beta_g^p \tilde{Y}_i^p + \beta_g^m \tilde{Y}_i^m + \epsilon_i$, where \tilde{Y}_i^o is the offspring's drinking variable with interacted fixed effects $\bar{\delta}_{ag}$ and σ_{yg} partialled out for computational and expositional ease (Correia 2015). The endogeneity problem arises from the correlation between \tilde{Y}_i^p or \tilde{Y}_i^m and ϵ_i . Traditional instrumental variable methods require instruments that are uncorrelated with ϵ_i , but finding such instruments is challenging, especially when two are needed for paternal and maternal drinking. The instruments would also need to induce a first-stage correlation within a directly comparable population of compliers, which is an extremely challenging requirement.

The copula correction method proposed by Park and Gupta (2012) offers a solution by accommodating the dependency structure between the endogenous regressors and the structural error term without requiring instruments. This method relies on modelling the joint distribution of the endogenous regressors and the error term, which is generally unknown. The first step in the method is to estimate the marginal distributions of the endogenous regressors using nonparametric density estimation. Once the marginal distributions for both endogenous regressors are estimated, the joint distribution function is constructed using Sklar's theorem. This theorem states that there exists a copula function that links the marginal distributions of the endogenous regressor and the structural error term to form a joint distribution. The copula function captures the scale-free dependence between variables after filtering out the influence of marginal distributions. Park and Gupta (2012) particularly suggest the Gaussian copula due to its general and robust properties and a great track record of empirical application. The method works best when the sample distribution of the endogenous regressors is as skewed as possible, as this enhances the identification of the correlation structure that drives endogeneity.

The theoretical properties of this estimator assume that the structural error term has a normal marginal distribution. However, simulations have shown that the normality assumption is not necessary and can be relaxed in practice (Park and Gupta 2012; Gui et al. 2023). To improve efficiency, which hinges on the distinction of correlations between the structural error term and the endogenous regressor, I apply the inverse hyperbolic sine transformation to offspring drinking to normalise ϵ_i due to its skewness. This transformation is similar to that used in empirical examples by Park and Gupta (2012, p. 583). Later, to calculate marginal effects on the original scale of the outcome and compare copula-corrected estimates with OLS, Duan's smearing estimate is applied (Norton 2022). Further details on the method and its practical use can be found in Park and Gupta (2012) or Gui et al. (2023). For inference, I use an offspring-clustered bootstrap approach for standard errors, as analytical errors are inappropriate in this context. The use of bootstrapped standard errors is also needed because I have partialled out fixed effects from the original model.

The top set in Table A.1 reports OLS results, which provide a baseline for comparing the copula-corrected estimates of intergenerational drinking transmission. Relative to the PPML estimates reported at the top of Table 6, the OLS estimate for males is almost twice as high as those produced by PPML. However, the current question is whether the OLS estimates are biased due to potential endogeneity issues, such as omitted variable bias and measurement errors. This is where the comparison with the copula-based method offers an answer.

The copula-based estimate at the bottom of Table A.1 addresses endogeneity by modelling the joint distribution of the endogenous regressors and the error term without requiring traditional instruments. This method provides a

Table A.1. Intergenerational drinking elasticity—consistency

	Dependent variable: Offspring drinking				N
	Paternal drinking		Maternal drinking		
	OLS estimator				
Son	0.136***	(0.029)	0.083+	(0.047)	43,817
Daughter	0.017	(0.016)	0.185***	(0.042)	
	Joint estimation with copulas (Park and Gupta 2012)				
Son	0.118**	(0.049)	0.072	(0.050)	43,817
Daughter	-0.030	(0.098)	0.162*	(0.061)	

+ p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.

Notes: Top uses offspring clustered CV1 errors. Bottom uses offspring clustered bootstrap errors.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023; intergenerational sample.

more robust but less efficient estimation by capturing the dependency structure between the regressors and the error term. In comparing OLS with copula-based estimates, the copula method slightly reduces the magnitude of the effects but maintains the same patterns across sexes as seen with other estimation methods.

It is possible to conduct a hypothesis test to determine whether coefficients across models for a corresponding dyad are the same. I use a bootstrap procedure to compare the parameters across the models after retrieving the point and variance estimates using the corresponding models. I cannot reject the null hypothesis of no difference, with a p-value of 0.153. This outcome is arguably driven by less biased estimates being much less efficient. Overall, there is no statistical reason to prefer the more complicated and less efficient models over a simpler and more efficient one.

To reiterate, the PPML estimator is preferred to OLS due to its tangible difference in point estimates and efficiency. Given the overwhelming number of zeros in the outcome variable, PPML is much better at handling marginal effects in this case. At the same time, the comparison of OLS and copula correction indicates that endogeneity is empirically negligible in my empirical setting. As a final comment, Park and Gupta (2012) showed that the copula correction method can also be applied to Poisson regression. In principle, I could directly compare the Poisson regression copula-corrected methods with my baseline estimates; however, in practice, I am using the statistical package by Gui et al. (2023).

B. Inference

Design-based view. I cluster standard errors at the offspring level, guided by a design-based perspective on inference. This approach has been recently advanced, emphasising mechanisms of data generation and sample-population relationships (Wooldridge 2023; Abadie et al. 2022; Xu 2020). The literature acknowledges the lack of a clear consensus or analytical guidelines on error clustering, particularly without a known randomisation mechanism for treatment, a challenge echoed in my study.

Clustering standard errors relaxes the assumption of independence by grouping residuals where units are parameterised to be independent. My sample consists of repeated observations of offspring across their ages, with observations across different offspring assumed to be independent. The key element of the design-based view is the retention indicator R_{it} , which in my case approaches zero, reflecting the sample of 6,310 offspring from Australia's 27 million, effectively mimicking a draw from an infinite population scenario. This affects asymptotic variance estimates, which in the design-based view are postulated to be a function of this indicator, thereby supporting offspring-level clustering. Even considering only the population of similar age (the median Australian age is 38), the retention indicator remains near zero, further justifying this approach.

Higher-level clustering is overly conservative from a design-based viewpoint and also practically impossible for my dataset. Offspring household-level clustering presents practical difficulties due to fluid affiliations, as offspring across years join new households in various capacities (e.g., as dependents, spouses, or heads of households). Clustering based on either parent's household is problematic due to frequent mismatches, particularly in separated families and non-biological parents, rendering such schemes arbitrary and impractical. Ignoring this fluidity violates the independence assumption across households, leading to inconsistent error estimates and creating a non-nested cluster structure—a known complexity in econometric literature.

This non-nested clustering arises when observations belong to multiple groups or change groups over time, often referred to as time-varying group membership in panel data contexts. While multi-way clustering techniques can address these complexities (Cameron et al. 2011), they are methodologically challenging in my dataset. The fluidity of offspring household affiliations and the ambiguity of parental household identifiers make identifying the additional dimensions for multi-way clustering challenging. This complexity reinforces the decision to cluster at the offspring level, which aligns with the data structure and provides an analytically unambiguous foundation for inference.

In terms of assignment mechanisms, we can conceptualise the environment created by parents for drinking transmission as analogous to a treatment arm in clinical trials with continuous treatment. Even in an idealised scenario (assuming away the practical challenge of mismatched parental households), clustering at the parent

household level would be akin to grouping arbitrary ranges of this continuous variable, which is inappropriate in clinical settings. Clustering at the offspring level, however, accounts for the individual-specific nature of the parental drinking ‘treatment’ while avoiding artificial discretisation. This aligns with both the data structure and sound statistical principles for continuous treatments, further supporting the decision to cluster at the offspring level.

Validity. Once the level of clustering is established, the focus shifts to selecting an appropriate variance estimator. A model-based perspective on clustering proves informative by providing a framework for inference validity, positing that the population is partitioned into uncorrelated clusters. While this view does not aid in selecting the clustering level, it offers a clearer analytical basis for determining the appropriate estimation method, as summarised by MacKinnon et al. (2023a).

A key practical decision is which cluster-robust variance estimator to use. The conventional estimator, CV0, proposed by Liang and Zeger (1986), subsequently adjusted for degrees of freedom and now labelled CV1, is the default in practical application. CV1 utilises squared residuals to capture the variance-covariance matrix (VCM) elements. However, these squared residuals may mechanically underestimate uncertainty when individual components of the matrix vary excessively relative to others. Although this issue is more common in smaller datasets, it can also persist in larger samples, as highlighted by MacKinnon and Webb (2017).

A decades-long known alternative that is finding renewed support in econometric literature is the CV3 estimator (Hansen 2025; MacKinnon et al. 2025; Lipsitz et al. 1990), which, relative to CV1, reweights residuals to better accommodate extreme values and influential elements in the VCM. When no excessively influential elements are present in the VCM, CV3 converges to CV1, maintaining consistency under both regular and irregular conditions. However, while computationally efficient algorithms for CV3 exist for linear models (MacKinnon et al. 2023b), for non-linear models, only a brute force version has been established, contributing to its main drawback of computational intensity. For my sample, this approach requires approximately 90 minutes on a CPU ranked in the 91.7th percentile according to UserBenchmark, using Stata’s native Poisson command

The top of Table B.1 presents results using the CV3 estimator. CV3 yields similar standard errors and statistical significance levels as the CV1 estimator used in the bottom part of Table 6, indicating that excessively influential clusters are either absent or present in quantities that do not distort asymptotic coverage. Here and in the main text, I follow Cox and Donnelly (2011, Ch. 8.4.3) and refer to significance at the 10% level (marked with +) as a suggestion of evidence against the hypothesis; 5% significance (marked with *) as modest evidence; and 1% significance (**) as strong evidence. Significance beyond this (***) is interpreted as very strong evidence.

As a concluding side note, CV3 employs a deletion principle, sequentially excluding each cluster and averaging the resulting leave-one-cluster-out estimates. This principle, which assesses the fitness of various model aspects through sequential deletion, also underpins the notion of leverage, quantifying influential observations or clusters (e.g., MacKinnon et al. 2023c). In Table C.2, I also apply this principle to evaluate the sensitivity of my gene-environment dichotomy estimates to different parent types.

Optimality. Robust inference estimates provide valid but not necessarily optimal standard errors. Efficiency depends on how closely the specified VCM approximates the true VCM. That mechanism was demonstrated in the improved efficiency observed when replacing OLS with PPML, transitioning from spherical errors to Poisson equidispersion (cf. top results in Table A.1 and Table 6).

Current econometric practice relies on a narrow application of Liang and Zeger’s (1986, Example 1) work, which shows cluster-robust variance estimates yield consistent standard errors even with unspecified intra-cluster

Table B.1. Baseline estimates—improved coverage and efficiency

	Dependent variable: Offspring drinking				N
	Paternal drinking		Maternal drinking		
Baseline results with CV3 estimator					
Son	0.092***	(0.017)	0.024+	(0.014)	43,817
Daughter	0.024	(0.024)	0.099***	(0.020)	
PPML with exchangeable working correlation matrix and CV1					
Son	0.093***	(0.017)	0.028*	(0.014)	43,817
Daughter	0.012	(0.018)	0.092***	(0.013)	

+ p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.

Notes: Top applies errors more robust to data irregularities. Bottom prespecifies errors for improved asymptotic convergence.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2022, intergenerational sample.

correlations. This approach sets all off-diagonal VCM elements to zero, misspecifying VCM by definition. As leading contributors in robust inference aptly note, "*It is remarkable that current econometric practice with clustered errors ignores the potential efficiency gains of FGLS*" (Cameron and Miller 2015, p. 326).

Greater efficiency can be achieved by specifying simple within-cluster correlations, such as equicorrelation, commonly used in clinical trials (Alexeev and Morton 2025). This approach enhances efficiency while preserving robustness to VCM misspecifications when paired with cluster-robust errors, fully utilising Liang and Zeger's (1986) methodology. As shown in Table B.1, this improved asymptotic approximation elevates evidence for maternal-to-son transmission from suggestive to modest. Further gains in efficiency may be realised through more intricate VCMs, such as autoregressive error structures.

Practically, if clustering at the offspring level leads to false positives, we could address this by clustering at a higher level, which might inflate standard errors, and then recover efficiency through a more complex VCM specification. This approach would likely produce conclusions similar to those derived from offspring-level clustering for this dataset, reinforcing the robustness of the findings across clustering levels. Thus, the choice of offspring-level clustering is both theoretically defensible and practically appropriate, with minimal risk of affecting the key conclusions.

In the main text, son-to-father and mother-to-daughter transmissions differed statistically only for average marginal effects, not elasticities (the baseline). Revisiting this with improved efficiency yields a p-value of 0.351, less than half of that when intracluster VCM elements are constrained to zero. Still inconclusive. Overall, if the exchangeable working correlation matrix is used throughout the main body of the text, all conclusions already presented are reinforced.

Placebo regressions. To empirically validate the inference, I implement a placebo regression approach, initially introduced by Bertrand et al. (2004) and now widely recommended in econometric practice (MacKinnon et al. 2023a). This method involves generating random treatments that mimic the structure of the actual treatment by reshuffling parental drinking variables on the offspring level within age strata. Conducting 5,000 replications, the observed rejection rates are close to the nominal 5%, providing evidence of the model's robustness.

The distribution of parameters obtained during these placebo reshufflings can also be used to form a randomisation inference test of significance. I apply this method to once again test the difference between son-to-father and mother-to-daughter transmission. Applying randomisation inference to this question yields a p-value of 0.892, which is higher than what the statistics shown in the main text.

Another related exercise follows the approach of Dohmen, Falk, Huffman, and Sunde (2011, p. 664), examining whether area-level selection biases the transmission estimates. In the main text, controlling for postcode-level drinking showed no significant impact on the parent-offspring transmission, suggesting that selection into specific areas is not driving the results. However, there are limitations to using controls to assess the extent of this bias, as these could be bad controls, potentially influencing the estimates in unintended ways. To reinforce the claim of no bias without relying on covariates, I reshuffle parental drinking variables within broader SA2-level area cells, accounting for postcode offspring sparsity. The disappearance of the parent-child drinking correlation after such reshuffling confirms that area characteristics do not substantially influence the transmission estimates.

This again points to the fact that the estimates of the transmission from the model are consistent, indicating that the model is correctly specified. This consistency in point estimates, in turn, guarantees that the standard errors are also consistent, as they rely on the same assumption of conditional mean independence. Thus, this exercise further strengthens the evidence for the causal nature of intergenerational transmission rather than merely reflecting shared factors.

C. Atypical dyads

Birth-non-birth sensitivities. The main specification in Section 4D implements a design-based split between birth and non-birth parents, estimated without post-treatment controls and with parent-type fixed effects by offspring sex (to

hold constant the composition of the non-birth group: step, foster, kin, grandparent, etc.). Omitting post-treatment controls avoids biasing elasticities downward via pathways that parental drinking may itself affect; including parent-type fixed effects prevents the birth-non-birth contrast from conflating biological status with shifts in who counts as ‘non-birth.’

To probe selection on observables, the first check in Table C.1 adds an offspring-schooling control (available near-universally, unlike, say, income that shrinks sample size) while retaining parent-type fixed effects. Equalising offspring along education (and thus much of the socio-economic pathways) leaves the qualitative pattern unchanged: daughters mirror mothers across biological status (both elasticities ≈ 0.10 , highly significant), whereas the father-to-son association remains attenuated and imprecise in non-birth dyads (about 0.05, n.s.). This supports the plausibility of the ‘approximately random with respect to drinking-related traits’ assumption discussed in the main text, at least along observed schooling differences.

Table C.1. Environmental channel—sensitivity checks

Dependent variable: Offspring drinking					
	Paternal drinking		Maternal drinking		N
	Birth	Non-birth	Birth	Non-birth	
Controlling for offspring schooling					
Son	0.091*** (0.019)	0.046 (0.031)	0.026+ (0.014)	0.026 (0.034)	40,747
Daughter	0.027 (0.024)	-0.013 (0.051)	0.097*** (0.020)	0.098*** (0.029)	
Parents N	37,380	3,367	39,522	1,225	
No parent-type fixed effects					
Son	0.095*** (0.019)	0.082** (0.028)	0.023 (0.014)	0.032 (0.034)	43,817
Daughter	0.026 (0.023)	-0.016 (0.044)	0.099*** (0.020)	0.103*** (0.023)	
Parents N	40,178	3,639	42,459	1,358	
Only birth/adoptive parent types					
Son	0.105*** (0.019)	0.058 (0.207)	0.014 (0.014)	-0.142 (0.196)	40,113
Daughter	0.027 (0.023)	-0.081 (0.251)	0.095*** (0.020)	0.134 (0.278)	
Parents N	39,906	207	39,972	141	

+ $p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Notes: The top panel adds offspring schooling; the middle panel excludes parent-type fixed effects; the bottom panel restricts to adoptive vs. birth labels.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023, intergenerational sample.

The imprecision of the birth-adoptive split also underscores why testing each non-birth category separately is infeasible: the categories are small, sparse, and often ambiguously coded. As a more robust alternative, I instead conduct a sequential deletion (jackknife) diagnostic. Table C.2 shows that excluding each non-birth type in turn leaves the overall birth-non-birth gap virtually unchanged, with only the female ‘missing’ category showing noisy variation consistent with sampling error. This stability confirms that the baseline estimates are not driven by any single subgroup and that the aggregated specification with parent-type fixed effects remains the most reliable approach.

Incomplete families. This specification broadens the sample to cases where one parental report at ages 12–18 is unobserved. I set the missing exposure to zero and add missing-status indicators so the model remains estimable under the baseline fixed effects. The four parental elasticities in Table C.3 are similar in sign and ranking to the

Next, Table C.1 removes parent-type fixed effects to show what happens if the non-birth mix is allowed to vary across families and ages. As expected, the non-birth father-to-son elasticity rises (to ≈ 0.08), while mother-to-daughter transmission is essentially unchanged (≈ 0.10). Reading these alongside the main-text estimates (with fixed effects) makes clear that the apparent father-to-son link in non-birth dyads is partly composition: once we hold the non-birth mix constant, it shrinks to ≈ 0.05 and loses precision. This is why the preferred specification includes parent-type fixed effects.

The cleaner conceptual alternative would be to estimate within a single, well-defined non-birth category where fixed effects are unnecessary. In the bottom panel of the table, I therefore report a birth-adoptive split restricted to the small subset with explicit adoptive labels. Because adoption flags are rare in the HILDA Survey (roughly 0.3–0.5% per parent), this sample is severely underpowered, and the resulting estimates are highly imprecise. I therefore treat them as descriptive. Directionally, they mirror the baseline with fixed effects, illustrating that the fixed-effect specification captures the same signal but with substantially greater precision.

Table C.2. Parent types influence—deletion diagnostics

Leave-out	Males	SE	Females	SE	N
Adoptive	0.541	0.306	-0.002	0.302	43,575
Step	0.924	0.549	0.190	0.236	41,462
Other	0.394	0.304	-0.024	0.306	43,735
Grandparent	0.524	0.306	-0.010	0.303	43,763
Uncle	0.525	0.306	-0.015	0.304	43,806
Foster parent	0.524	0.306	-0.001	0.302	43,777
No parent	0.468	0.331	0.026	0.301	43,490
Missing	0.558	0.320	-2.526	1.241	42,951

Notes: (Birth-Adoptive)/Birth with delta method errors (se) after excluding one parent type from the sample.

Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023, intergenerational sample.

complete-dyad baseline—father-son and mother-daughter dominate; mother-son is modest; father-daughter is small but detectable. At the same time, the sample means in this specification are not the same as in the main sample: average offspring drinking is higher here (sons: 276.05 vs. 270.63; daughters: 145.33 vs. 141.12), while average parental exposures are lower once zero-fill is applied (paternal: 218.95 vs. 253.12; maternal: 106.97 vs. 111.27). These shifts confirm that the incomplete-dyad sample is compositionally different.

Crucially, the estimand changes. Incomplete dyads pool heterogeneous family structures and reporting regimes (solo parenting, non-co-residence, attrition, category miscoding). That mixture does not map cleanly onto the vertical channel in the rational-transmission framework, so these coefficients cannot be read as causal parental transmission. The descriptive means align with this: when a father’s report is missing, offspring drink more on average (sons: 297.13 vs. 273.32; daughters: 158.69 vs. 143.33). When a mother’s report is missing, the gaps are remarkably large (sons: 396.25 vs. 273.72; daughters: 251.78 vs. 143.45). In the regression, the missing-status indicators are likewise associated with higher expected drinking, underscoring that selection and measurement differences—rather than additional transmission—are being captured.

Methodologically, this exercise represents a sample-definition sensitivity rather than an estimator fix. Its endogeneity concerns are comparable to those that arise when dyads are estimated separately, as shown in Table 9: both relax the joint identification that anchors the baseline, and both invite heterogeneity outside the maintained common-exposure design. I therefore retain the complete-dyad specification as the primary estimand and treat Table C.3 as descriptive support for external validity: broadening the sample leaves the qualitative pattern intact but introduces selection that makes mechanism inference unclear.

Table C.3. Including incomplete dyads

	Dependent variable: Offspring drinking			Mean	
	Paternal drinking		Maternal drinking		
Son	0.069***	(0.0150)	0.034**	(0.012)	276.05
Daughter	0.041*	(0.018)	0.082***	(0.016)	145.33
Mean	218.95		106.97		
N					51,000

+ p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.
Notes: Baseline PPML now includes offspring with only one observed parent by zero-filling the missing exposure and adding missing-parent indicators.
Source: HILDA Survey 2001–2023, intergenerational sample.

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Data Availability Statement. This study uses the restricted-release, unit-record version of the HILDA Survey, Waves 1–23. Access to the HILDA Survey data is granted to authorised researchers under licence from the Australian Government Department of Social Services and is administered by the Melbourne Institute. The data are not publicly available, but licensed users may apply for access through the National Centre for Longitudinal Data at: <https://doi.org/10.26193/J4NSZO>. Researchers wishing to access the restricted-release unit-record files (including the parent-type identifiers used in this paper) must obtain additional approval from the HILDA Survey data custodians. The findings and views reported in this paper are those of the author and should not be attributed to either the Australian Government Department of Social Services or the Melbourne Institute.

Dedication. Andrey and Masha—my dear siblings—whose lives have been less fortunate than mine have been on my mind throughout the work on this manuscript. Thank you for my childhood. This little work is for you.

Acknowledgement. I extend my sincere gratitude to Alberto Bisin, Pablo Mitnik, Don Weatherburn, Benjamin Spivak, and Gary Solon for their valuable feedback. Special thanks to Jenny Williams for her thorough review, which significantly enhanced the manuscript’s quality. I am particularly grateful to Alberto Bisin for guidance on theoretical work, to Gary Solon for insights on life-cycle bias in non-income contexts, and to both Pablo Mitnik and Gary Solon for reviewing the regression specification. I also thank Mark Wooden, Michael Windle, Bruce Sacerdote, and several other colleagues for brief comments and helpful suggestions during the final revision. Any remaining errors are my sole responsibility.

References

- Abadie, A, Athey, S, Imbens, GW, and Wooldridge, JM. 2022. "When Should You Adjust Standard Errors for Clustering?" *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 138, no. 1 (October): 1–35. ISSN: 0033-5533. [10.1093/qje/qjac038](https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjac038). (Cited on page 15).
- Adlaf, EM and Smart, RG. 1985. "Drug Use and Religious Affiliation, Feelings and Behaviour." *British Journal of Addiction* 80 (2): 163–171. [10.1111/j.1360-0443.1985.tb03267.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1360-0443.1985.tb03267.x). (Cited on page 9).
- Agrawal, A, Heath, AC, Grant, JD, et al. 2006. "Assortative Mating for Cigarette Smoking and for Alcohol Consumption in Female Australian Twins and their Spouses." *Behavior Genetics* 36, no. 4 (July): 553–566. ISSN: 1573-3297. [10.1007/s10519-006-9081-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10519-006-9081-8). (Cited on page 2).
- Aiken, A, Wadolowski, M, Bruno, R, et al. 2015. "Cohort Profile: The Australian Parental Supply of Alcohol Longitudinal Study (APSALS)." *International Journal of Epidemiology* 46, no. 2 (May). ISSN: 0300-5771. [10.1093/ije/dyv051](https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyv051). (Cited on page 2).
- Akerlof, GA and Kranton, RE. 2000. "Economics and Identity." *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 115, no. 3 (August): 715–753. ISSN: 0033-5533. [10.1162/003355300554881](https://doi.org/10.1162/003355300554881). (Cited on page 2).
- Alexeev, S. 2020. "The role of imputed rents in intergenerational income mobility in three countries." *Journal of Housing Economics* 49:101710. ISSN: 1051-1377. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhe.2020.101710>. (Cited on page 11).
- Alexeev, S and Morton, RL. 2025. "Cluster trials inference with CARE." *ResearchGate preprint (under review in Statistics in Medicine)*, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/376204429_Cluster_trials_inference_with_CARE. (Cited on page 17).
- Alexeev, S and Weatherburn, D. 2021. "The Australian ready-to-drink beverages tax missed its target age group." *International Journal of Drug Policy* 95:103399. ISSN: 0955-3959. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2021.103399>. (Cited on page 4).
- Andersen, C. 2021. "Intergenerational health mobility: Evidence from Danish registers." *Health Economics* 30 (12): 3186–3202. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hec.4433>. (Cited on page 7).
- Auld, MC. 2005. "Smoking, Drinking, and Income." *Journal of Human Resources* XL (2): 505–518. [10.3368/jhr.XL.2.505](https://doi.org/10.3368/jhr.XL.2.505). (Cited on pages 2, 9).
- Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS). 2021. *Births, Australia*. Statistical Report 3301.0. Accessed on 26 September, 2024. Australian Bureau of Statistics. <https://www.abs.gov.au/statistics/people/population/births-australia/latest-release>. (Cited on page 13).
- Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW). 2018. *Impact of alcohol and illicit drug use on the burden of disease and injury in Australia: Australian Burden of Disease Study 2011*. Report, Australian Burden of Disease Study series 17. Cat. no. BOD 19. Accessed on September 19, 2024. Canberra: Australian Institute of Health and Welfare, December. <https://www.aihw.gov.au/reports/burden-of-disease/impact-alcohol-illicit-drug-use-on-burden-disease>. (Cited on page 1).
- . 2022. *Australia's mothers and babies*. Report. Accessed on September 25, 2022. Canberra: Australian Institute of Health and Welfare, September. <https://www.aihw.gov.au/reports/mothers-babies/australias-mothers-babies>. (Cited on page 5).
- Baillon, A, Bleichrodt, H, and Granic, GD. 2022. "Incentives in surveys." *Journal of Economic Psychology* 93:102552. ISSN: 0167-4870. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joep.2022.102552>. (Cited on page 4).
- Baum, CF. 2010. "Stata tip 88: Efficiently evaluating elasticities with the margins command." *The Stata Journal* 10 (2): 309–312. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/1536867X1001000212>. (Cited on page 8).
- Becker, G. 1981. *A Treatise on the Family*. Harvard University Press. ISBN: 9780674906969. <https://books.google.com.au/books?id=BxVoAAAIAAJ>. (Cited on page 2).
- Bertrand, M, Duflo, E, and Mullainathan, S. 2004. "How Much Should We Trust Differences-in-Differences Estimates?" *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 119 (1): 249–275. ISSN: 00335533, 15314650, accessed April 15, 2023. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25098683>. (Cited on page 17).
- Bisin, A and Verdier, T. 2000. "“Beyond the Melting Pot”: Cultural Transmission, Marriage, and the Evolution of Ethnic and Religious Traits." *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 115, no. 3 (August): 955–988. ISSN: 0033-5533. [10.1162/003355300554953](https://doi.org/10.1162/003355300554953). (Cited on page 2).
- . 2001. "The Economics of Cultural Transmission and the Dynamics of Preferences." *Journal of Economic Theory* 97 (2): 298–319. ISSN: 0022-0531. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jeth.2000.2678>. (Cited on page 2).
- . 2011. "Chapter 9 - The Economics of Cultural Transmission and Socialization," edited by Benhabib, J, Bisin, A, and Jackson, MO, 1:339–416. *Handbook of Social Economics*. North-Holland. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-53187-2.00009-7>. (Cited on pages 2, 7, 12).
- Björklund, A, Lindahl, M, and Plug, E. 2006. "The Origins of Intergenerational Associations: Lessons from Swedish Adoption Data." *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 121, no. 3 (August): 999–1028. ISSN: 0033-5533. [10.1162/qjec.121.3.999](https://doi.org/10.1162/qjec.121.3.999). (Cited on pages 6, 11, 12).

- Blume, LE, Brock, WA, Durlauf, SN, and Ioannides, YM. 2011. "Chapter 18 - Identification of Social Interactions," edited by Benhabib, J, Bisin, A, and Jackson, MO, 1:853-964. *Handbook of Social Economics*. North-Holland. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-53707-2.00001-3>. (Cited on page 2).
- Boggess, M and MacDonald, K. 2013. "When I use the `eyex` option of margins, what is it actually computing and how does it relate to the coefficients of the loglinear model?" *StataCorp*, accessed October 1, 2022. <https://www.stata.com/support/faqs/statistics/elasticities-using-margins/>. (Cited on page 8).
- Boyd, R and Richerson, P. 1988. *Culture and the Evolutionary Process*. Biology, Anthropology, Sociology. University of Chicago Press. ISBN: 9780226069333. <https://books.google.com.au/books?id=MBg4oBsCKU8C>. (Cited on page 2).
- Bray, JW, Hinde, JM, and Aldridge, AP. 2018. "Alcohol use and the wage returns to education and work experience." *Health Economics* 27 (2): e87–e100. [10.1002/hec.3565](https://doi.org/10.1002/hec.3565). (Cited on pages 1, 11).
- Caliendo, M and Hennecke, J. 2022. "Drinking is different! Examining the role of locus of control for alcohol consumption." *Empirical Economics* 63 (5): 2785–2815. ISSN: 1435-8921. [10.1007/s00181-022-02219-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00181-022-02219-3). (Cited on pages 1, 11).
- Cameron, AC and Miller, DL. 2015. "A practitioner's guide to cluster-robust inference." *Journal of human resources* 50 (2): 317–372. http://cameron.econ.ucdavis.edu/research/Cameron_Miller_JHR_2015_February.pdf. (Cited on page 17).
- Cameron, AC, Gelbach, JB, and Miller, DL. 2011. "Robust Inference With Multiway Clustering." *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics* 29 (2): 238–249. [10.1198/jbes.2010.07136](https://doi.org/10.1198/jbes.2010.07136). (Cited on page 15).
- Campbell, JM and Oei, TP. 2010. "A cognitive model for the intergenerational transference of alcohol use behavior." *Addictive Behaviors* 35 (2): 73–83. ISSN: 0306-4603. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addbeh.2009.09.013>. (Cited on page 2).
- Casey, B, Jones, RM, and Hare, TA. 2008. "The Adolescent Brain." *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* 1124 (1): 111–126. <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1440.010>. (Cited on page 10).
- Cattaneo, MD, Crump, RK, Farrell, MH, and Feng, Y. 2024. "On Binscatter." *American Economic Review* 114, no. 5 (May): 1488–1514. [10.1257/aer.20221576](https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.20221576). (Cited on page 4).
- Cavalli-Sforza, LL and Feldman, MW. 1981. *Cultural Transmission and Evolution: A Quantitative Approach*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press. ISBN: 9780691082837. <https://books.google.com.au/books?id=FDfBDwAAQBAJ>. (Cited on page 2).
- Cawley, J and Ruhm, CJ. 2011. "Chapter Three - The Economics of Risky Health Behaviors." In *Handbook of Health Economics*, edited by Pauly, MV, Mcguire, TG, and Barros, PP, 2:95–199. *Handbook of Health Economics*. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-53592-4.00003-7>. (Cited on page 8).
- Chen, J and Roth, J. 2023. "Logs with Zeros? Some Problems and Solutions." *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 139, no. 2 (December): 891–936. ISSN: 0033-5533. [10.1093/qje/qjad054](https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjad054). (Cited on page 7).
- Chernozhukov, V, Fernández-Val, I, Meier, J, van Vuuren, A, and Vella, F. 2024. "Conditional Rank-Rank Regression." *arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.06387*, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.06387>. (Cited on page 7).
- Chetverikov, D and Wilhelm, D. 2023. "Inference for rank-rank regressions." *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.15512*, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.15512>. (Cited on page 7).
- Clites, BL, Hofmann, HA, and Pierce, JT. 2023. "The Promise of an Evolutionary Perspective of Alcohol Consumption." *Neuroscience Insights* 18:26331055231163589. [10.1177/26331055231163589](https://doi.org/10.1177/26331055231163589). (Cited on page 12).
- Conroy, RM. 2005. "Stings in the Tails: Detecting and Dealing with Censored Data." *The Stata Journal* 5 (3): 395–404. [10.1177/1536867X0500500308](https://doi.org/10.1177/1536867X0500500308). (Cited on page 4).
- Correia, S. 2015. *HDFE: Stata module to partial out variables with respect to a set of fixed effects*. Statistical Software Components s457985. Boston College Department of Economics, March. <https://ideas.repec.org/c/boc/bocode/s457985.html>. (Cited on page 14).
- Cox, D and Donnelly, C. 2011. *Principles of Applied Statistics*. Cambridge University Press. ISBN: 9781139503549. <https://books.google.com.au/books?id=BMLMGr4kbQYC>. (Cited on page 16).
- Davis, J, Deutscher, N, and Mazumder, B. 2025. *Intergenerational Mobility in Measures of Wellbeing: Consumption, Health and Life Satisfaction*. Working Paper 34407. National Bureau of Economic Research. [10.3386/w34407](https://doi.org/10.3386/w34407). (Cited on page 2).
- Denton, M and Walters, V. 1999. "Gender differences in structural and behavioral determinants of health: an analysis of the social production of health." *Social Science and Medicine* 48 (9): 1221–1235. ISSN: 0277-9536. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536\(98\)00421-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536(98)00421-3). (Cited on page 2).

- Dohmen, T, Falk, A, Huffman, D, and Sunde, U. 2011. "The Intergenerational Transmission of Risk and Trust Attitudes." *The Review of Economic Studies* 79, no. 2 (November): 645-677. ISSN: 0034-6527. [10.1093/restud/rdr027](https://doi.org/10.1093/restud/rdr027). (Cited on pages 2, 3, 9, 17).
- Dohmen, T, Falk, A, Huffman, D, Sunde, U, Schupp, J, and Wagner, GG. 2011. "Individual Risk Attitudes: Measurement, Determinants, and Behavioral Consequences." *Journal of the European Economic Association* 9, no. 3 (June): 522-550. ISSN: 1542-4766. [10.1111/j.1542-4774.2011.01015.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1542-4774.2011.01015.x). (Cited on page 4).
- Donovan, JE and Molina, BSG. 2011. "Childhood Risk Factors for Early-Onset Drinking." PMID: 21906502, *Journal of Studies on Alcohol and Drugs* 72 (5): 741-751. [10.15288/jsad.2011.72.741](https://doi.org/10.15288/jsad.2011.72.741). (Cited on page 11).
- Falk, A, Becker, A, Dohmen, T, Enke, B, Huffman, D, and Sunde, U. 2018. "Global Evidence on Economic Preferences." *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 133, no. 4 (May): 1645-1692. ISSN: 0033-5533. [10.1093/qje/qjy013](https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjy013). (Cited on page 4).
- Fitzgerald, JM. 2011. "Attrition in Models of Intergenerational Links Using the PSID with Extensions to Health and to Sibling Models." *The B.E. Journal of Economic Analysis & Policy* 11 (3): Article 2. [10.2202/1935-1682.2868](https://doi.org/10.2202/1935-1682.2868). (Cited on page 13).
- Grawe, ND. 2006. "Lifecycle bias in estimates of intergenerational earnings persistence." *Labour Economics* 13 (5): 551-570. ISSN: 0927-5371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.labeco.2005.04.002>. (Cited on page 6).
- Greaves, L, Poole, N, and Brabete, AC. 2022. "Sex, gender, and alcohol use: Implications for women and low-risk drinking guidelines." *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19 (8): 4523. ISSN: 1660-4601. [10.3390/ijerph19084523](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19084523). (Cited on page 11).
- Gui, R, Meierer, M, Schilter, P, and Algesheimer, R. 2023. "REndo: Internal Instrumental Variables to Address Endogeneity." *Journal of Statistical Software* 107 (3): 1-43. [10.18637/jss.v107.i03](https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v107.i03). (Cited on pages 14, 15).
- Habib, C. 2012. "The transition to fatherhood: A literature review exploring paternal involvement with identity theory." *Journal of Family Studies* 18 (2-3): 103-120. [10.5172/jfs.2012.18.2-3.103](https://doi.org/10.5172/jfs.2012.18.2-3.103). (Cited on page 10).
- Halliday, T. 2020. "Intergenerational Health Mobility." In *Handbook of Labor, Human Resources and Population Economics*, edited by Zimmermann, KF, 1-22. Cham: Springer International Publishing. ISBN: 978-3-319-57365-6. [10.1007/978-3-319-57365-6_368-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-57365-6_368-1). (Cited on page 2).
- Hansen, BE. 2025. "Standard Errors for Difference-in-Difference Regression." *Journal of Applied Econometrics* 40 (3): 291-309. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jae.3110>. (Cited on page 16).
- Hardin, JW and Hilbe, JM. 2018. *Generalized Linear Models and Extensions, Second Edition*. A Stata Press publication. Taylor & Francis. ISBN: 978-1-59718-225-6. <https://www.stata.com/bookstore/generalized-linear-models-and-extensions/>. (Cited on page 9).
- Hauk, E and Saez-Marti, M. 2002. "On the Cultural Transmission of Corruption." *Journal of Economic Theory* 107 (2): 311-335. ISSN: 0022-0531. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jeth.2001.2956>. (Cited on page 2).
- Hingson, RW, Heeren, T, and Winter, MR. 2006. "Age at Drinking Onset and Alcohol Dependence: Age at Onset, Duration, and Severity." *Archives of Pediatrics & Adolescent Medicine* 160, no. 7 (July): 739-746. ISSN: 1072-4710. [10.1001/archpedi.160.7.739](https://doi.org/10.1001/archpedi.160.7.739). (Cited on page 10).
- Hinnosaar, M and Liu, EM. 2022. "Malleability of Alcohol Consumption: Evidence from Migrants." *Journal of Health Economics* 85:102648. ISSN: 0167-6296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhealeco.2022.102648>. (Cited on page 12).
- Holmila, M and Raitasalo, K. 2005. "Gender differences in drinking: Why do they still exist?" *Addiction* 100 (12): 1763-1769. [10.1111/j.1360-0443.2005.01249.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1360-0443.2005.01249.x). (Cited on page 11).
- Homel, J and Warren, D. 2019. "The Relationship Between Parent Drinking and Adolescent Drinking: Differences for Mothers and Fathers and Boys and Girls." PMID: 30676187, *Substance Use & Misuse* 54 (4): 661-669. [10.1080/10826084.2018.1531429](https://doi.org/10.1080/10826084.2018.1531429). (Cited on page 1).
- Howe, LJ, Lawson, DJ, Davies, NM, et al. 2019. "Genetic evidence for assortative mating on alcohol consumption in the UK Biobank." *Nature Communications* 10, no. 1 (November): 5039. ISSN: 2041-1723. [10.1038/s41467-019-12424-x](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-12424-x). (Cited on page 2).
- Jääntti, M and Jenkins, SP. 2015. "Chapter 10 - Income Mobility." In *Handbook of Income Distribution*, edited by Atkinson, AB and Bourguignon, F, 2:807-935. Handbook of Income Distribution. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-59428-0.00011-4>. (Cited on pages 7, 8, 10, 11).
- Johnson, KA and Jennison, KM. 1992. "The Drinking-Smoking Syndrome and Social Context." *International Journal of the Addictions* 27 (7): 749-792. [10.3109/10826089209068767](https://doi.org/10.3109/10826089209068767). (Cited on page 9).
- Kaplan, G, La Cava, G, and Stone, T. 2018. "Household Economic Inequality in Australia." *Economic Record* 94 (305): 117-134. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-4932.12399>. (Cited on page 11).
- Karlsson, P, Magnusson, C, and Svensson, J. 2016. "Does the familial transmission of drinking patterns persist into young adulthood? A 10-year follow up." *Drug and Alcohol Dependence* 168:45-51. ISSN: 0376-8716. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugalcdep.2016.08.630>. (Cited on page 7).

- Kaynak, Ö, Winters, KC, Cacciola, J, Kirby, KC, and Arria, AM. 2014. "Providing Alcohol for Underage Youth: What Messages Should We Be Sending Parents?" PMID: 24988258, *Journal of Studies on Alcohol and Drugs* 75 (4): 590–605. [10.15288/jsad.2014.75.590](https://doi.org/10.15288/jsad.2014.75.590). (Cited on page 1).
- Keyes, KM, Grant, BF, and Hasin, DS. 2008. "Evidence for a closing gender gap in alcohol use, abuse, and dependence in the United States population." *Drug and Alcohol Dependence* 93 (1): 21–29. ISSN: 0376-8716. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugalcdep.2007.08.017>. (Cited on page 5).
- Killingsworth, B. 2006. "Drinking stories' from a playgroup: Alcohol in the lives of middle-class mothers in Australia." *Ethnography* 7 (3): 357–384. [10.1177/1466138106067905](https://doi.org/10.1177/1466138106067905). (Cited on page 10).
- Kuntsche, E, Knibbe, R, Gmel, G, and Engels, R. 2006. "Who drinks and why? A review of socio-demographic, personality, and contextual issues behind the drinking motives in young people." *Addictive Behaviors* 31 (10): 1844–1857. ISSN: 0306-4603. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addbeh.2005.12.028>. (Cited on page 9).
- Lee, CI and Solon, G. 2009. "Trends in Intergenerational Income Mobility." *The Review of Economics and Statistics* 91 (4): 766–772. [10.1162/rest.91.4.766](https://doi.org/10.1162/rest.91.4.766). (Cited on pages 3, 5, 8).
- Liang, KY and Zeger, SL. 1986. "Longitudinal data analysis using generalized linear models." *Biometrika* 73, no. 1 (April): 13–22. ISSN: 0006-3444. [10.1093/biomet/73.1.13](https://doi.org/10.1093/biomet/73.1.13). (Cited on pages 16, 17).
- Lillard, DR and Dorofeeva, Z. 2015. "Smoking in Russia and Ukraine Before, During, and After the Soviet Union." In *Life-course smoking behavior: Patterns and national context in ten countries*. Oxford University Press, May. ISBN: 9780199389100. [10.1093/med/9780199389100.003.0009](https://doi.org/10.1093/med/9780199389100.003.0009). (Cited on page 12).
- Lim, S, Han, CE, Uhlhaas, PJ, and Kaiser, M. 2013. "Preferential Detachment During Human Brain Development: Age- and Sex-Specific Structural Connectivity in Diffusion Tensor Imaging (DTI) Data." *Cerebral Cortex* 25, no. 6 (December): 1477–1489. ISSN: 1047-3211. [10.1093/cercor/bht333](https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bht333). (Cited on page 10).
- Lipsitz, SR, Laird, NM, and Harrington, DP. 1990. "Using the Jackknife to Estimate the Variance of Regression Estimators from Repeated Measures Studies." *Communications in Statistics - Theory and Methods* 19 (3): 821–845. [10.1080/03610929008830234](https://doi.org/10.1080/03610929008830234). (Cited on page 16).
- Livingston, M and Callinan, S. 2015. "Underreporting in Alcohol Surveys: Whose Drinking Is Underestimated?" PMID: 25486405, *Journal of Studies on Alcohol and Drugs* 76 (1): 158–164. [10.15288/jsad.2015.76.158](https://doi.org/10.15288/jsad.2015.76.158). (Cited on page 4).
- Livingston, M, Raninen, J, Slade, T, Swift, W, Lloyd, B, and Dietze, P. 2016. "Understanding trends in Australian alcohol consumption – an ageperiodcohort model." *Addiction* 111 (9): 1590–1598. <https://doi.org/10.1111/add.13396>. (Cited on page 5).
- Lundberg, I, Johnson, R, and Stewart, BM. 2021. "What Is Your Estimand? Defining the Target Quantity Connects Statistical Evidence to Theory." *American Sociological Review* 86 (3): 532–565. [10.1177/00031224211004187](https://doi.org/10.1177/00031224211004187). (Cited on page 7).
- Luria, E and Katz, YJ. 2019. "Parent-child transmission of religious and secular values in Israel." *Journal of Beliefs & Values* 0 (0): 1–16. [10.1080/13617672.2019.1688472](https://doi.org/10.1080/13617672.2019.1688472). (Cited on page 2).
- MacKinnon, JG, Nielsen, MØ, and Webb, MD. 2023a. "Cluster-robust inference: A guide to empirical practice." *Journal of Econometrics*, ISSN: 0304-4076. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconom.2022.04.001>. (Cited on pages 16, 17).
- . 2023b. "Fast and reliable jackknife and bootstrap methods for cluster-robust inference." *Journal of Applied Econometrics* 38 (5): 671–694. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jae.2969>. (Cited on page 16).
- . 2023c. "Leverage, influence, and the jackknife in clustered regression models: Reliable inference using summlust." *The Stata Journal* 23 (4): 942–982. [10.1177/1536867X231212433](https://doi.org/10.1177/1536867X231212433). (Cited on page 16).
- . 2025. "Cluster-robust jackknife and bootstrap inference for logistic regression models." *Econometric Reviews* 0 (0): 1–29. [10.1080/07474938.2025.2515161](https://doi.org/10.1080/07474938.2025.2515161). (Cited on page 16).
- MacKinnon, JG and Webb, MD. 2017. "Wild Bootstrap Inference for Wildly Different Cluster Sizes." *Journal of Applied Econometrics* 32 (2): 233–254. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jae.2508>. (Cited on page 16).
- Macleod, J, Hickman, M, Bowen, E, Alati, R, Tilling, K, and Smith, GD. 2008. "Parental drug use, early adversities, later childhood problems and children's use of tobacco and alcohol at age 10: birth cohort study." *Addiction* 103 (10): 1731–1743. [10.1111/j.1360-0443.2008.02301.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1360-0443.2008.02301.x). (Cited on page 2).
- Maggs, JL and Schulenberg, JE. 2005. "Initiation and Course of Alcohol Consumption among Adolescents and Young Adults." In *Recent Developments in Alcoholism: Alcohol Problems in Adolescents and Young Adults*, edited by Galanter, M, Lowman, C, Boyd, GM, Faden, VB, Witt, E, and Lagressa, D, 29–47. Boston, MA: Springer US. ISBN: 978-0-306-48626-5. [10.1007/0-306-48626-1_2](https://doi.org/10.1007/0-306-48626-1_2). (Cited on page 10).
- Mazumder, B. 2005. "Fortunate Sons: New Estimates of Intergenerational Mobility in the United States Using Social Security Earnings Data." *The Review of Economics and Statistics* 87 (2): 235–255. [10.1162/0034653053970249](https://doi.org/10.1162/0034653053970249). (Cited on page 5).

- McLaughlin, A, Campbell, A, and McColgan, M. 2016. "Adolescent Substance Use in the Context of the Family: A Qualitative Study of Young People's Views on Parent-Child Attachments, Parenting Style and Parental Substance Use." PMID: 27606719, *Substance Use & Misuse* 51 (14): 1846-1855. [10.1080/10826084.2016.1197941](https://doi.org/10.1080/10826084.2016.1197941). (Cited on page 9).
- Meurk, CS, Broom, A, Adams, J, Hall, W, and Lucke, J. 2014. "Factors influencing women's decisions to drink alcohol during pregnancy: findings of a qualitative study with implications for health communication." *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth* 14, no. 1 (July): 246. issn: 1471-2393. [10.1186/1471-2393-14-246](https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2393-14-246). (Cited on page 10).
- Mitnik, PA and Grusky, DB. 2020. "The Intergenerational Elasticity of What? The Case for Redefining the Workhorse Measure of Economic Mobility." *Sociological Methodology* 50 (1): 47-95. [10.1177/0081175019886613](https://doi.org/10.1177/0081175019886613). (Cited on page 7).
- Northcote, J and Livingston, M. 2011. "Accuracy of Self-Reported Drinking: Observational Verification of 'Last Occasion' Drink Estimates of Young Adults." *Alcohol and Alcoholism* 46, no. 6 (September): 709-713. issn: 0735-0414. [10.1093/alcalc/agr138](https://doi.org/10.1093/alcalc/agr138). (Cited on page 4).
- Norton, EC. 2022. "The inverse hyperbolic sine transformation and retransformed marginal effects." *The Stata Journal* 22 (3): 702-712. [10.1177/1536867X221124553](https://doi.org/10.1177/1536867X221124553). (Cited on page 14).
- Oster, E. 2019. "Unobservable Selection and Coefficient Stability: Theory and Evidence." *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics* 37 (2): 187-204. [10.1080/07350015.2016.1227711](https://doi.org/10.1080/07350015.2016.1227711). (Cited on page 9).
- Pape, H, Rossow, I, and Brunborg, GS. 2018. "Adolescents drink less: How, who and why? A review of the recent research literature." *Drug and Alcohol Review* 37 (S1): S98-S114. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dar.12695>. (Cited on page 5).
- Park, S and Gupta, S. 2012. "Handling Endogenous Regressors by Joint Estimation Using Copulas." *Marketing Science* 31 (4): 567-586. [10.1287/mksc.1120.0718](https://doi.org/10.1287/mksc.1120.0718). (Cited on pages 3, 4, 14, 15).
- Pauley, A, Metcalf, M, Buono, M, et al. 2024. "When a man drinks alcohol it's cool but when a woman drinks she is a hoe: A qualitative exploration of alcohol, gender, stigma, and sexual assault in Moshi, Tanzania." *PLOS Global Public Health* 4 (2): 1-21. [10.1371/journal.pgph.0002382](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgph.0002382). (Cited on page 11).
- Peters, BL and Stringham, E. 2006. "No booze? You may lose: Why drinkers earn more money than nondrinkers." *Journal of Labor Research* 27, no. 3 (December): 411-421. issn: 1936-4768. [10.1007/s12122-006-1031-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12122-006-1031-y). (Cited on page 2).
- Plug, E. 2004. "Estimating the Effect of Mother's Schooling on Children's Schooling Using a Sample of Adoptees." *American Economic Review* 94, no. 1 (March): 358-368. [10.1257/000282804322970850](https://doi.org/10.1257/000282804322970850). (Cited on page 11).
- Poelen, EAP, Engels, RCME, Scholte, RHJ, Boomsma, DI, and Willemsen, G. 2009. "Predictors of problem drinking in adolescence and young adulthood." *European child & adolescent psychiatry* 18, no. 6 (February): 345-352. [10.1007/s00787-009-0736-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00787-009-0736-x). (Cited on page 2).
- Reeves, R. 2022. *Of Boys and Men: Why the modern male is struggling, why it matters, and what to do about it*. Swift Press. ISBN: 9781800750555. <https://books.google.com.au/books?id=WmZoEAAAQBAJ>. (Cited on page 10).
- Rehm, J, Baliunas, D, Borges, GLG, et al. 2010. "The relation between different dimensions of alcohol consumption and burden of disease: an overview." *Addiction* 105 (5): 817-843. [10.1111/j.1360-0443.2010.02899.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1360-0443.2010.02899.x). (Cited on page 9).
- Rehm, J, Mathers, C, Popova, S, Thavorncharoensap, M, Teerawattananon, Y, and Patra, J. 2009. "Global burden of disease and injury and economic cost attributable to alcohol use and alcohol-use disorders." *The Lancet* 373 (9682): 2223-2233. issn: 0140-6736. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(09\)60746-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(09)60746-7). (Cited on page 1).
- Sacerdote, B. 2007. "How Large are the Effects from Changes in Family Environment? A Study of Korean American Adoptees." *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 122, no. 1 (February): 119-157. issn: 0033-5533. [10.1162/qjec.122.1.119](https://doi.org/10.1162/qjec.122.1.119). (Cited on page 12).
- . 2011. "Chapter 1 - Nature and Nurture Effects On Children's Outcomes: What Have We Learned From Studies of Twins And Adoptees?," edited by Benhabib, J, Bisin, A, and Jackson, MO, 1:1-30. *Handbook of Social Economics*. North-Holland. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-53187-2.00001-2>. (Cited on pages 11, 12).
- Sassi, F. 2015. *Tackling Harmful Alcohol Use Economics and Public Health Policy: Economics and Public Health Policy*. OECD Publishing. ISBN: 9789264181069. <https://books.google.com.au/books?id=i7w-CQAQBAJ>. (Cited on page 1).
- Savegnago, M. 2016. "Igmobil: A Command for Intergenerational Mobility Analysis in Stata." *The Stata Journal* 16 (2): 386-402. [10.1177/1536867X1601600207](https://doi.org/10.1177/1536867X1601600207). (Cited on page 11).
- Schildberg-Hörisch, H. 2018. "Are Risk Preferences Stable?" *Journal of Economic Perspectives* 32, no. 2 (May): 135-54. [10.1257/jep.32.2.135](https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.32.2.135). (Cited on page 4).
- Schmidt, CM and Tauchmann, H. 2011. "Heterogeneity in the intergenerational transmission of alcohol consumption: A quantile regression approach." *Journal of Health Economics* 30 (1): 33-42. issn: 0167-6296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhealeco.2010.09.005>. (Cited on pages 7, 8).

- Sharmin, S, Kypri, K, Khanam, M, Wadolowski, M, Bruno, R, and Mattick, R. 2017. "Parental Supply of Alcohol in Childhood and Risky Drinking in Adolescence: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis." *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 14, no. 3 (March): 287. issn: 1660-4601. [10.3390/ijerph14030287](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph14030287). (Cited on page 1).
- Silva, S and Tenreiro, S. 2022. "The Log of Gravity at 15." *Portuguese Economic Journal* 21, no. 3 (September): 423-437. issn: 1617-9838. [10.1007/s10258-021-00203-w](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10258-021-00203-w). (Cited on page 7).
- Skeer, MR, McCormick, MC, Normand, SLT, Mimiaga, MJ, Buka, SL, and Gilman, SE. 2011. "Gender Differences in the Association Between Family Conflict and Adolescent Substance Use Disorders." *Journal of Adolescent Health* 49 (2): 187-192. issn: 1054-139X. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2010.12.003>. (Cited on page 2).
- Stack, S and Bankowski, E. 1994. "Divorce and Drinking: An Analysis of Russian Data." *Journal of Marriage and Family* 56 (4): 805-812. issn: 00222445, 17413737. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/353593>. (Cited on page 9).
- Thompson, O. 2014. "Genetic mechanisms in the intergenerational transmission of health." *Journal of Health Economics* 35:132-146. issn: 0167-6296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhealeco.2014.02.003>. (Cited on page 11).
- Törrönen, J, Roumeliotis, F, Samuelsson, E, Kraus, L, and Room, R. 2019. "Why are young people drinking less than earlier? Identifying and specifying social mechanisms with a pragmatist approach." *International Journal of Drug Policy* 64:13-20. issn: 0955-3959. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2018.12.001>. (Cited on page 5).
- Treno, AJ, Marzell, M, Gruenewald, PJ, and Holder, H. 2014. "A Review of Alcohol and Other Drug Control Policy Research." PMID: 24565316, *Journal of Studies on Alcohol and Drugs, Supplement*, no. s17, 98-107. [10.15288/jsads.2014.s17.98](https://doi.org/10.15288/jsads.2014.s17.98). (Cited on page 13).
- Verweij, KJH and Abdellaoui, A. 2022. "Partner-choice genetics in Japan." *Nature Human Behaviour* (September). issn: 2397-3374. [10.1038/s41562-022-01439-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-022-01439-y). (Cited on page 2).
- Walker, B and Munford, L. 2023. "The social capital penalty paid by teetotalers." *SSM - Population Health* 23:101437. issn: 2352-8273. [10.1016/j.ssmph.2023.101437](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmph.2023.101437). (Cited on pages 1, 11).
- Watson, N. 2022. "New generations of respondents: Assessing the representativity of the HILDA Survey's child sample." *Longitudinal and Life Course Studies* (Bristol, UK) 13 (3): 465-489. [10.1332/175795921X16349086588358](https://doi.org/10.1332/175795921X16349086588358). (Cited on page 13).
- Wickrama, KAS, Conger, RD, Wallace, LE, and Elder, GH. 1999. "The Intergenerational Transmission of Health-Risk Behaviors: Adolescent Lifestyles and Gender Moderating Effects." *Journal of Health and Social Behavior* 40 (3): 258-272. issn: 00221465. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2676351>. (Cited on page 2).
- Windle, M and Windle, RC. 2012. "Intergenerational Relations for Drinking Motives: Invariant for Same- and Opposite-Sex Parent-Child Dyads?" PMID: 22152663, *Journal of Studies on Alcohol and Drugs* 73 (1): 63-70. [10.15288/jsad.2012.73.63](https://doi.org/10.15288/jsad.2012.73.63). (Cited on pages 2, 9).
- Wolfe, JD. 2009. "Age at First Birth and Alcohol Use." PMID: 20099447, *Journal of Health and Social Behavior* 50 (4): 395-409. [10.1177/002214650905000402](https://doi.org/10.1177/002214650905000402). (Cited on page 10).
- Wooldridge, JM. 1992. "Some Alternatives to the Box-Cox Regression Model." *International Economic Review* 33 (4): 935-955. issn: 00206598, 14682354, accessed January 3, 2024. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2527151>. (Cited on page 8).
- . 2023. "What is a standard error? (And how should we compute it?)" *Journal of Econometrics* 237 (2, Part A): 105517. issn: 0304-4076. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconom.2023.105517>. (Cited on page 15).
- Xu, R. 2020. "Potential outcomes and finite-population inference for M-estimators." *The Econometrics Journal* 24, no. 1 (July): 162-176. issn: 1368-4221. [10.1093/ectj/utaa022](https://doi.org/10.1093/ectj/utaa022). (Cited on page 15).
- Yu, J. 2003. "The association between parental alcohol-related behaviors and children's drinking." *Drug and Alcohol Dependence* 69 (3): 253-262. issn: 0376-8716. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0376-8716\(02\)00324-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0376-8716(02)00324-1). (Cited on page 1).
- Yu, J and Perrine, MWB. 1997. "The Transmission of Parent/Adult-Child Drinking Patterns: Testing a Gender-Specific Structural Model." *The American Journal of Drug and Alcohol Abuse* 23 (1): 143-165. [10.3109/00952999709001693](https://doi.org/10.3109/00952999709001693). (Cited on page 2).